

ABSTRACT

Revenue Administration - Jurisdiction - Bifurcation of Viluppuram District - Creation of Kallakurichi new District - Orders - Issued.

Revenue and Disaster Management Department,
Revenue Administration Wing, [RA 1(1)] Section

G.O.(Ms) No.424

Dated: 12.11.2019

விகாரி, ஐப்பசி 26,
திருவள்ளூர் ஆண்டு 2050

Read:

From the Additional Chief Secretary / Commissioner of Revenue Administration, Letter No.Ser-3(4)/1816/ 2019, dated 14.06.2019 and 26.09.2019.

ORDER:

The Hon'ble Chief Minister during the reply to debate on the Governor's address on the floor of the Assembly on 08.01.2019 has made the following announcement:-

"Viluppuram District, being a big District, will be bifurcated for administrative convenience and a new District with Kallakurichi as its Head Quarters will be formed. For this newly created District an IAS Officer will be appointed as Special Officer at the earliest."

2. Based on the above announcement, the Additional Chief Secretary / Commissioner of Revenue Administration has visited Viluppuram District on 05.02.2019 and 06.02.2019 and held discussions with the Hon'ble M.P. and M.L.A.'s, District Collector, Viluppuram, Elected Representatives Leaders of political parties and all sections of people, has sent necessary proposals and requested the Government to issue necessary orders.

3. The Government have examined the proposal of the Additional Chief Secretary / Commissioner of Revenue Administration in detail and pass the following orders:-

- (i) Viluppuram District is bifurcated into Viluppuram and Kallakurichi Districts as follows:-
 - a. Viluppuram District with Head Quarters at Viluppuram.
 - b. Kallakurichi District with Head Quarters at Kallakurichi.

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- (ii) The Jurisdiction of the Viluppuram and Kallakurichi Districts are indicated in the Annexure -I to this order.
- (iii) Thiruvannainallur new Taluk is formed with Head Quarters at Thiruvannainallur with 3 Firkas (70 Villages) viz., Thiruvannainallur (25 Villages), Sithalingamadam (21 Villages) of existing Tirukoilur Taluk and Arasur (24 Villages) of the existing Ulundurpettai Taluk are attached with Viluppuram Revenue Division and Viluppuram District. (Details are indicated in Annexure - III in this order)
- (iv) Kandachipuram Taluk is transferred from existing Tirukoilur Revenue Division to Viluppuram Revenue Division.
- (v) Kalvarayan Hills, new Taluk is formed with Head Quarters at Kalvarayan Hills, with 2 Firkas (44 Villages) viz. Kalvarayan Hills (18 Villages) of existing Sankarapuram Taluk and Vellimalai (26 Villages) of existing Chinnasalem Taluk are attached with Kallakurichi Revenue Division / District. (Details are indicated in Annexure-IV to this order)
- (vi) 13 supporting staff to the Special Officer (Details are indicated in the Annexure -II to this order) are created for a period of six months from the date of appointment or till the necessity for it ceases whichever is earlier to work out all the works for re-organisation and creation of Kallakurichi new District.
- (vii) The Special Officer is instructed to take charge of the administration of the new district immediately. The incumbent of the post will be eligible to draw, besides pay, the other allowances admissible under the orders in force.
- (viii) The Special Officer is instructed to take into account the staff sanctioned in Annexure -II while submitting proposals to Government for sanction of staff in accordance with the staff pattern for a District.
- (ix) The Special Officer of Kallakurichi new District is instructed to attend the works relating to separation of Records of Kallakurichi new District and all such activities which are incidental consequent on the formation of the new District.
- (x) Till a new building is constructed for Kallakurichi new District, sanction is accorded to fix the rent for accommodation of the office of the Special Officer as per PWD rules and as per G.O.(Ms) No.329, Finance (Salaries) Department, dated 30.8.2001.

- (xi) Sanction is accorded for a sum of Rs.32,30,000/- (Rupees Thirty two lakh thirty thousand only) towards the purchase of two new vehicles of which one is for the official use of Special Officer of Kallakurichi new District (cost of vehicle is Rs.12,80,000/-) and the other one is for the use of VIP's of the Kallakurichi new District (cost of vehicle is Rs.19,50,000/-)
- (xii) Sanction is accorded for a sum of Rs.64,00,200/- (Rupees Sixty four lakh two hundred only) for incurring expenditure to the supporting staff to the Special Officer.

4. The District Collector, Viluppuram District and the Special Officer, Kallakurichi are requested to take immediate action to give effect to this order.

5. The Principal Secretary / Commissioner of Revenue Administration is requested to send necessary proposals of recurring and non-recurring expenditure and creation of staff for the creation of Kallakurichi District, Thiruvannainallur and Kalvarayan Hills Taluks.

6. The details of recurring and non-recurring expenditure and creation of posts for newly created Kallakurichi District, Thiruvannainallur and Kalvarayan Hills Taluks, necessary orders will be issued separately.

7. The delimitation of the territorial wards of Village Panchayats, Panchayat Union and District Panchayats have already been notified under the Tamil Nadu Panchayats Act, 1994 (Tamil Nadu Act 21 of 1994) and thereby the delimitation exercise for the ensuing local body elections has already been completed. Notwithstanding the notification to bifurcate the districts, the process started already to conduct the ensuing Local Body Elections will be continued as per the order of the Hon'ble Supreme Court dated 17.07.2019 in W.P.(Civil) No. 1267/2018. After the ensuing Local Body Elections, the process of modification if any, with regard to local bodies will be taken up by the Government.

8. The Principal Secretary / Commissioner of Revenue Administration is authorised to draw the amount sanctioned in para 3 (xi & xii) above and make payment in advance to the suppliers. The District Collector, Viluppuram District is authorised to sanction the payment of charges towards fuel etc., incurred by the Special Officer. The Government also permit the District Treasury officer, Viluppuram to admit the claims of the District Collector, Viluppuram District pertaining to the expenditure relating to the Kallakurichi new District.

9. The expenditure sanctioned at para 3(xi) above for the purchase of new cars should be debited to the following head of account:-

**"2053.00 - District Administration - 093 - District Establishments -AA Collectors and Magistrates -21 Motor Vehicles-01-purchase"
(D.P.Code 2053 00 093 AA 2113)"
IFHRMS (Rs.32,30,000)**

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10. The expenditure sanctioned at para 3 (xii) above on the staff should be debited to the following head of account:-

**"2053.00 - District Administration - 093 - District Establishments -I Non- Plan - AA Collectors and Magistrates -01 Salaries"
D.P.Code 2053 00 093 AA 01 06)"
IFHRMS (Rs.64,00,200)**

11. The expenditure sanctioned in paragraphs 8 and 9 above constitute an item of "New Instrument of Service". Approval of Legislature will be obtained in due course. Pending approval of Legislature, the expenditure will be met initially by sanction of an advance from the contingency fund for which order will be issued by Finance (BG-1) Department. The Principal Secretary / Commissioner of Revenue Administration is requested to apply in the prescribed format enclosing a copy of the orders for the requirement amount. He is also requested to send necessary proposal to Finance Department for inclusion of the expenditure to supplementary estimates for the year 2019-2020 and for bringing it to the notice of the Legislature in due course.

12. This order issues with the concurrence of Finance Department C.No.56030 / Finance (Revenue) / 2019, dated 06.11.2019 vide its U.O.No.56483 / CMPC/2019, dated 07.11.2019 and ASL No.2024 (Two Thousand Twenty Four)

(By order of the Governor)

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

To

The Principal Secretary / Commissioner of
Revenue Administration, Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.
The Additional Chief Secretary / Commissioner of
Land Administration, Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.
The Additional Chief Secretary / Commissioner Land Reforms,
Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.
The Principal Secretary / Commissioner of Urban Land Ceiling
and Urban Land Tax, Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.
The Director of Survey and Settlement, Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.
The District Collector, Viluppuram District
The Special Officer concerned.
The District Treasury Officer, Viluppuram District.
All District Collectors.
The Registrar and Census Commissioner of India,
No.2/4, Mansingh Road, New Delhi-100 011.
The Accountant General, (PAO) Chennai - 600 009.
The Accountant General, (A&E/G&SSA) Chennai - 600 018.
The Pay and Accounts Officer, Chennai - 600 104.
The Director of Stationery and Printing, Chennai-600 002.

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Copy to:

All Secretaries to Government, Chennai - 600 009.
All Departments of Secretariat, Chennai - 600 009.
All Head of Departments.
All Sections in Revenue and Disaster Management Department,
Chennai - 600 009. (Follow-up action to be taken by the concerned section
in respect of sanction of Additional staff, further continuance, Furniture etc)
The Registrar, High Court of Madras, Chennai - 600 104. (with covering letter)
The Public (Special A) Department, Chennai - 600 009.
The Director of Census Operation, Rajaji Bhavan, Chennai - 600 090.
The Public (Elections) Department, Chennai - 600 009.
The Hon'ble Chief Minister's Office, Chennai - 600 009.
The Special Personal Assistant to Hon'ble Minister
(Revenue & Disaster Management) Chennai - 600 009.
The Principal Private Secretary to the Principal Secretary,
Revenue and Disaster Management Department, Chennai - 600 009.
The Finance (Revenue) / (CMPC) Department, Chennai - 600 009.
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//Forwarded by Order//

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12/11/19
Section Officer

ANNEXURE-I

G.O.(Ms.) No. 424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Various details of newly created Kallakurichi district and residual Viluppuram District

Sl. No.	Description	Viluppuram District before bifurcation	Kallakurichi New District	Viluppuram District after bifurcation
1	2	3	4	5
1	Head quarters	Viluppuram	Kallakurichi	Viluppuram
2	Area (Sq. Km)	7245.91(Sq. Km)	3520.37(Sq. Km)	3725.54(Sq. Km)
3	Population	3463284	1370281	2093003
4	No. of Revenue Division with name	1.Viluppuram 2.Tindivanam 3.Tirukoilur 4.Kallakurichi	1.Kallakurichi 2.Tirukoilur	1.Viluppuram 2.Tindivanam
5	No. of Revenue Taluks with name	1.Viluppuram 2.Vikravandi 3.Vanur 4.Tindivanam 5.Gingee 6.Melmalaiyanur 7.Marakkanam 8.Tirukoilur 9.Ulundurpet 10.Kandachipuram 11.Kallakurichi 12.Sankarapuram 13.Chinnasalem	1.Kallakurichi 2.Sankarapuram 3.Chinnasalem 4.Tirukoilur 5.Ulundurpet 6.Kalvarayan Hills (new)	1.Viluppuram 2.Vikravandi 3.Vanur 4. Thiruvonnainallur (new) 5.Tindivanam 6.Gingee 7.Melmalaiyanur 8.Marakkanam 9.Kandachipuram
6	No. of Assembly Constituencies with name	1.Viluppuram 2.Vikravandi 3.Tindivanam 4.Vanur 5.Mailam 6.Gingee 7.Ulundurpet 8.Tirukoilur 9.Rishivandiyam 10.Kallakurichi 11.Sankarapuram	1.Tirukoilur (part) 2.Kallakurichi 3.Sankarapuram 4.Ulundurpet (Part) 5.Rishivandiyam	1.Viluppuram 2.Vikravandi 3.Tindivanam 4.Vanur 5.Mailam 6.Gingee 7.Thirukovilur (part) 8.Ulundurpet (part)
7	No. of Parliament Constituencies with name	1.Viluppuram 2.Arni(Part) 3.Kallakurichi(Part)	1.Kallakurichi(Part)	1.Viluppuram 2.Arni(Part)
8	No. of Municipalities with name	1.Viluppuram 2.Tindivanam 3.Kallakurichi	1.Kallakurichi	1.Viluppuram 2.Tindivanam

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Sl. No.	Description	Viluppuram District before bifurcation	Kallakurichi New District	Viluppuram District after bifurcation
9	No.of Panchayat Unions with name	1.Tirukoilur 2.Mugaiyur 3.Thiruvonnainallur 4.Tirunavalur 5.Ulundurpet 6.Kanai 7.Kolliyanur 8.Kandamangalam 9.Vikravandi 10.Olakkur 11.Mailam 12.Marakanam 13.Vanur 14.Gingee 15.Vallam 16.Melmalayanur 17.Kallakurichi 18.Chinnasalem 19.Rishivandiyam 20.Sankarapuram 21.Thiyagadurugam 22.Kalvarayan hills	1.Kallakurichi 2.Chinnasalem 3.Rishivandiyam 4.Sankarapuram 5.Thiyagadurugam 6.Kalvarayan hills 7.Tirukoilur 8.Ulundurpet 9.Thirunavalur	1.Kanai 2.Kolliyanur 3.Kandamangalam 4.Vikiravandi 5.Olakkur 6.Mailam 7.Marakanam 8.Vanur 9.Gingee 10.Vallam 11.Melmalayanur 12.Mugaiyur 13.Thiruvonnainallur
10	No of Town Panchayat with Name	1. Chinnasalem 2. Vadakkunanthal 3. Sankarapuram 4. Thiyagadurugam 5. Ulundupet 6. Thiruvonnainallur 7. Tirukovilur 8. Arakandanallur 9. Manalurpet 10. Valavanur 11. Vikravandi 12. Kottakuppam 13. Marakanam 14. Gingee 15. Ananthapuram	1. Chinnasalem 2. Vadakkunanthal 3. Sankarapuram 4. Thiyagadurugam 5. Ulundupet 6. Tirukovilur 7. Manalurpet	1. Valavanur 2. Vikravandi 3. Kottakuppam 4. Marakanam 5. Gingee 6. Ananthapuram 7. Thiruvonnainallur 8. Arakandanallur
11	No. of Firkas	57	23	34
12	No. of Revenue Villages	1490	558	932
13	No. of Village Panchayats	1099	406	693
14	Name of the Villages Far away from the District Head quarters	Varam village (150 km) in Sankarapuram Taluk	Varam village (80 km) in Sankarapuram Taluk	Tazhangadu (83 Km) in Marakkanam Taluk

Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)

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ANNEXURE- II

G.O.(Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

List of Supporting Staff to the Special Officer and Scale of Pay

Sl.No.	Name of the Post	Level	Scale of Pay	No.of Post
1	Personal Assistant (in the cadre of Deputy Collector)	22	Rs.56,100/- to Rs.1,77,500/-	1 (one)
2	Tahsildar	20	Rs.37,700/- to Rs.1,19,500/-	1 (one)
3	Assistant	10	Rs.20,600/- to Rs.65,500/-	1 (one)
4	Steno - Typist (Grade 2)	11	Rs.35,400 to Rs.1,12,400/-	1 (one)
5	Steno - Typist (Grade 3)	10	Rs.20,600/- to Rs.65,500/-	1 (one)
6	Typist (Junior Assistant -cum- Typist)	8	Rs.19,500/- to Rs.62,000/-	1 (one)
7	Office Assistant	1	Rs.15,700/- to Rs.50,000/-	5 (Five)
8	Driver*	8	Rs.19,500/- to Rs.62,000/-	2 (Two)

*** to be filled up after the vehicle is made available.**

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

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ANNEXURE - III

G.O.(Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Details of Thiruvennainallur new taluk in Viluppuram District

Sl. No.	Details	Thiruvennainallur New Taluk
1	HeadQuarters	Thiruvennainallur
2	Area(Sq.Km)	248.43 (or) 250
3	Population	1,60,954
4	Name of Revenue Division	Viluppuram
5	Name of Assembly constituencies	1.Tirukoilur (Part) 2.Ulundurpettai (Part)
6	Name of Parliament constituency	Viluppuram
7	No. of Municipalities	---
8	No. of Panchayat Unions	1.Thiruvennainallur
9	No. of Town Panchayats	1.Thiruvennainallur
10	No. of Firkas	3 1.Thiruvennainallur 2.Sithalingamadam 3.Arasur
11	No.of Revenue villages	70
12	No.of Village Panchayats	58

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Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

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ANNEXURE -IV

G.O. (Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Details of Kalvarayan Hills New Taluk in newly created Kallakurichi District

Sl. No.	Details	Kalvarayan Hills New Taluk
1	Head Quarters	Kalvarayan Hills
2	Area(Sq.Km)	550.70
3	Population	41025
4	Name of Revenue Division	Kallakurichi
5	Name of Assembly constituencies	Sankarapuram
6	Name of Parliament constituency	Kallakurichi
7	No. of Municipalities	---
8	No. of Panchayat Unions	Vellimalai (1)
9	No. of Town Panchayats	-
10	No. of Firkas	2 1. Kalvarayan Hills 2. Vellimalai
11	No.of Revenue villages	44
12	No.of Village Panchayats	15

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

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ANNEXURE - V

G.O. (Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Profile of Viluppuram District after bifurcation

Division	Taluks	Population	Area in Sq. Kms.	No. of Firkas	No. of villages	No. of panchayat unions	No. of municipalities	No. of own Panchayats
Viluppuram	Viluppuram	421957	416.00	4	123	3	1	2
	Vikravandi	293454	478.00	4	116	1	--	1
	Vanur	195476	451.89	4	81	1	--	1
	Kandachipuram	151027	234.00	2	62	1	--	1
	Thiruvannainallur (new)	160954	248.43	3	70	1	-	-
Tindivanam	Tindivanam	316342	657.22	7	174	3	1	--
	Gingee	283025	580.00	4	166	1	--	2
	Melmalaiyanur	139728	345.00	3	80	1	--	--
	Marakkanam	131040	315.00	3	60	1	--	1
Total		2093003	3725.54	34	932	13	2	8

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

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ANNEXURE -VI

G.O. (Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Profile of newly created Kallakurichi District

Division	Taluk	Population	Area in Sq. Kms.	No. of Firkas	No. of villages	No. of panchayat unions	No. of Municipalities	No. of town Panchayats
Tirukoilur	Tirukoilur	173612	302.83	3	74	1	-	2
	Ulundurpet	322018	654.60	6	151	2	-	1
Kallakurichi	Kallakurichi	277303	538.58	4	93	2	1	1
	Sankarapuram	361975	1045.38	5	133	2	-	1
	Chinnasalem	194348	428.28	3	63	1	-	2
	Kalvarayan Hills (new)	41025	550.70	2	44	1	-	-
Total		1370281	3520.37	23	558	09	01	7

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

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ANNEXURE - VII

G.O.(Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Retained Areas in Viluppuram District

Taluks in Viluppuram District			No. of Firkas			No. of Revenue Villages		
			Existing	Addition	Newly Restructured	Existing	Addition	Newly Restructured
Viluppuram Division	1	Viluppuram	4	0	4	123	0	123
	2	Vikkaravandi	4	0	4	116	0	116
	3	Vanur	4	0	4	81	0	81
	4	Kandachipuram	2	0	2	62	0	62
	5	Thiruvannainallur (newly proposed Taluk)	0	3	3	0	70	70
Tindivanam Division	1	Tindivanam	7	0	7	174	0	174
	2	Marakkanam	3	0	3	60	0	60
	3	Gingee	4	0	4	166	0	166
	4	Melmalyanur	3	0	3	80	0	80
Total			31	3	34	862	70	932

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

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12/11/19
Section Officer

ANNEXURE -VIII

G.O. (Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Included Areas in newly created Kallakurichi District

Taluks in Kallakurichi new District			No. of Firkas			No. of Revenue Villages		
			Existing	Addition / Deletion	Newly Restructured	Existing	Addition / Deletion	Newly Restructured
Kallakurichi Revenue Division	1	Kallakurichi	4	0	4	93	0	93
	2	Chinnasalem	4	-1	3	89	-26	63
	3	Sankarapuram	6	-1	5	151	-18	133
	4	Kalvarayan Hills (newly proposed Taluk)	0	2	2	0	44	44
Tirukoilur Revenue Division	1	Tirukoilur	5	-2	3	120	-46	74
	2	Ulundurpettai	7	-1	6	175	-24	151
Total			26	-3	23	628	-70	558

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

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ANNEXURE- IX

G.O.(Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Assembly Constituencies in newly created Kallakurichi District and residual Viluppuram District

Sl. No.	Viluppuram District before bifurcation	Kallakurichi new District	Viluppuram District after bifurcation
1	70. Gingee	-	70. Gingee
2	71. Mailam	-	71. Mailam
3	72. Tindivanam (SC)	-	72. Tindivanam (SC)
4	73. Vanur (SC)	-	73. Vanur (SC)
5	74. Viluppuram	-	74. Viluppuram
6	75. Vikaravanadi	-	75. Vikaravanadi
7	76. Tirukoilur	76. Thirukovilur (Part)	76. Thirukovilur (Part)
8	77. Ulundurpet	77. Ulundurpet (part)	77. Ulundurpet (Part)
9	78. Rishivandhiyam	78. Rishivandhiyam	
10	79. Sankarapuram	79. Sankarapuram	
11	80. Kallakurichi	80. Kallakurichi	

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

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Section Officer

ANNEXURE - X**G.O.(Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019****Taluk wise list of Villages in Residual Viluppuram District**

Name of the Taluk	Name of the Firka	Sl. No.	Village No.	Name of the Village		
I. VILUPPURAM	1. Kandamangalam	1	94	ARPISAMPALAIYAM		
		2	118	KANDAMANGALAM		
		3	103	SORNAVUR(MELPADI)		
		4	105	KALANJI KUPPAM		
		5	104	SORNAVUR(KILPADI)		
		6	95	SIRUVANDADU		
		7	101	SORAPPUR		
		8	112	PALLIPPUDUPPATTU		
		9	113	KOTTAMBAKKAM		
		10	114	PALLICHCHERI		
		11	119	NAVAMALKAPPER		
		12	109	PAKKAM (NORTH)		
		13	109	PAKKAM (SOUTH)		
		14	120	PALLITTENNAL		
		15	107	KRISHNAPURAM		
		16	106	PERICHCHAMBAKKAM		
		17	98	METTUPPALAIYAM		
		18	102	RAMAPAKKAM		
		19	99	KONGAMBATTU		
		20	100	CHOKKAMBATTU		
		21	117	NAVAMAL MARUDUR		
		22	111	MITTAMANDAGAPPATTU		
		23	110	KONDUR		
		24	115	PALLI NERIYANUR		
		25	97	PARASUREDDIPALAIYAM		
		26	96	MOKSHAKULAM		
		27	76	PUVARASANKUPPAM		
		28	108	VIRANAM		
		29	116	ALIYUR		
		2. Valavanur	30	60	SALAIAGARAM	
				31	64	TODARNDANUR
				32	56	POYYAPAKKAM
				33	57	MADIRIMANGALAM
				34	58	MELPATHI
				35	83	KALLAPPATTU
				36	90	GANGARAMPALAIYAM
				37	89	MANAKUPPAM
				38	88	PUDUR. V
				39	91	MALRAJANKUPPAM
				40	72	VENGATADRI AGARAM
				41	75	VADAVAMBALAM
				42	74	KALLIPPATTU.C
				43	77	PANCHAMADEVI
				44	59	KOLIYANUR

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		45	80	PANANGUPPAM
		46	84	SENGADU
		47	85	VADUGANATHANKUPPAM
		48	82	NARAIYUR
		49	87	ILANGADU
		50	86	PEDDUREDDIKUPPAM
		51	92	KUDIMIYANKUPPAM
		52	79	SALAIYAMPALAIYAM (E)
		53	79	SALAIYAMPALAIYAM (W)
		54	65	NANNATTAMPALAIYAM
		55	78	MALAVARAYANUR
		56	93	VALAVANUR
		57	81	KUMARAKUPPAM
		58	70	SERNDANUR
		59	69	(TEN) KUCHCHIPPALAIYAM
		60	71	PILLUR
		61	73	ARASAMANGALAM
	3. Kanai	62	16	KALPATTU (EAST)
		63	16	KALPATTU (WEST)
		64	15	MAMBALAMPATTU
		65	17	SIRUVAKKUR
		66	18	TELI
		67	20	KARINGALIPPATTU
		68	36	VENMANIYATTUR
		69	35	V.KOTTAMANGALAM
		70	19	KONUR
		71	13	KANGIYANUR
		72	21	KANAI
		73	23	VAILAMUR
		74	22	KUPPAM
		75	12	AGARAM CHITTAMUR
		76	7	VENGANDUR
		77	11	ARIYUR
		78	37	KAPPUR
		79	24	PERUMBAKKAM
		80	32	VENKTESAPURAM
		81	33	ORUKODI
		82	34	SATTIPATTU
		83	31	TOKAIPADI
		84	14	MALLIKAIPATTU
		85	3	PALLIYANDUR
		86	2	KOLIPPATTU
		87	1	ARIYALUR (TIRUKKAI)
		88	4	KEDAR
		89	5	VIRAMUR
		90	6	VALAPPATTU

	4.Viluppuram	91	27	VIRATTIKUPPAM
		92	26	ALATTUR
		93	9	CHOLAMPUNDI
		94	8	ASARANKUPPAM
		95	10	IDAPPALAIYAM
		96	28	NANNADU
		97	25	VEDAMBATTU
		98	42	PEDAGAM
		99	63	PANAMPATTU
		100	66	ANANGUR
		101	41	KANDAMANADI
		102	67	KAVANIPPAKKAM
		103	47	CHITTATTUR TIRUKKAI
		104	46	DALAVANUR (TIRUVADI)
		105	45	KONGARAKONDAN
		106	43	ATTIYUR (TIRUVADI)
		107	44	VELIYAMBAKKAM
		108	29	VALUDUREDDI
		109	68	TIRUPPACHCHANUR
		110	40	KANDAMBAKKAM
		111	30	KONDANGI
		112	49	KULATTUR
		113	48	ARIYALUR (VILLUPURAM)
114	38	MARAGATHAPURAM		
115	39	KANDIYAMADAI		
116	53	KAKUPPAM		
117	54	KILPERUMBAKKAM		
118	61	MAHARAJAPURAM		
119	55	ERUMANANTHANGAL		
120	52	VILUPPURAM		
121	62	MARUDUR		
122	51	PUNTOTTAM		
123	50	SALAMEDU		
II. THIRUVENNAINALLUR (NEW)	1.Sittilingamadam**	1	81	SITTILINGAMADAM (EAST)
		2	81	SITTILINGAMADAM (WEST)
		3	77	VADAKKUNEMALI
		4	78	ATTANDAMARUDUR
		5	76	MUDALUR
		6	75	KULAPPAKKAM(AVIYUR)
		7	93	PUDUPPALAIYAM (TIRUVENNAINALLUR)
		8	90	PENNAIVALAM
		9	80	MEYYUR(CHIDAMBARAM)
		10	74	KATTUPPAIYUR
		11	84	ELRAMBATTU
		12	83	KODIYUR
		13	82	KUNNATTUR (TIRUVENNAINALLUR)
		14	89	VIRANAMBATTU
15	79	MARUDUR (VADA)		
16	87	ARUNGURUKKAI		

		17	92	AKKANUR
		18	91	PAVANDUR
		19	85	MALAIYANUR (VADA)
		20	86	VILLIVALAM
		21	88	KONALAVADI (TIRUKKOVILUR)
	2.Tiruvonnainallur **	22	104	TIRUVENNAINALLUR (SOUTH)
		23	104	TIRUVENNAINALLUR (NORTH)
		24	103	EMAPPUR (SOUTH)
		25	103	EMAPPUR (NORTH)
		26	95	KONGARAYANUR
		27	107	SIRUMADURAI
		28	108	SIRUVANUR
		29	110	ENADIMANGALAM
		30	100	MANAKKUPPAM
		31	112	ERALUR
		32	111	SATTANUR (TIRUVENNAINALLUR)
		33	97	EDAIYAR.T
		34	96	PAIYUR
		35	109	MARANGIYUR
		36	113	SEMMAR
		37	114	MELMANGALAM
		38	115	VALAIYAMBATTU
		39	116	KILMANGALAM
		40	99	ELANDURAI
		41	94	ANDARAYANUR
		42	98	PANAPPAKKAM
		43	105	MALAVARAYANUR (TIRUKKOVILUR)
		44	106	CHINNASEVALAI
		45	101	TADUTTALKONDUR
		46	102	MALAIYAMBATTU
	3. Arasur **	47	125	ANATTUR
		48	127	POYYARASUR
		49	126	KUMARAMANGALAM (TIRUKKOVILUR)
		50	121	KARAPPATTU
		51	122	TANIYALAMBATTU (MEL)
		52	124	SEMANGALAM
		53	123	TANIYALAMBATTU (KIL)
		54	128	ARASUR
		55	114	TIRUMUNDICHARAM
		56	113	ALANGUPPAM
		57	120	IRUVELIPPATTU
		58	119	PERANGIYUR
		59	117	TENMANGALAM
		60	116	KURANUR
		61	115	KANNARAMPATTU

		62	129	KANDALVADI	
		63	107	ANAIVARI	
		64	106	MADAMBATTU	
		65	108	PARUKKAMBATTU	
		66	110	ARUMBATTU	
		67	109	ATTIPPATTU	
		68	118	KARADIPPAKKAM	
		69	111	CHITTANANGUR	
		70	112	MAMANDUR	
III. KANDACHIPURAM	1.Arakandanallur	1	18	ARAKANDANALLUR	
		2	9	DEVANUR . T	
		3	19	ANDILI	
		4	27	KOLLUR	
		5	7	MANAMPUNDI	
		6	6	KUDAMURUTTI	
		7	8	KOTTAMARUDUR	
		8	5	(ADUR)KULAPPAKKAM	
		9	4	KODUKKAPPATTU	
		10	3	VELAKKULAM	
		11	10	NAYANUR	
		12	11	ARASANKUPPAM	
		13	13	PULIKKAL	
		14	2	VASANTAKRISHNAPURAM	
		15	1	ADICHCHANUR	
		16	26	PUTTUR(VELANDAI)	
		17	23	KILKONDUR	
		18	17	VADAGARAITAYANUR	
		19	16	VELLAMPUTTUR	
		20	15	TIRUMALAIPPATTU	
		21	25	MELKONDUR	
		22	24	PARANUR	
		23	21	EMAPPER	
		24	22	ARUMALAI	
		25	20	NERKUNAM	
		26	12	VIRAPANDI	
		27	37	ODDAMBATTU	
		28	36	ARUNAPURAM	
		29	14	KALLANDAL	
		30	39	ADUKKAM	
		31	38	TANDARAI	
		2. Mugaiyur	32	52	MUGAIYUR
			33	51	SATYAKANDANUR
			34	56	AYANDUR
			35	57	GUDALUR. A
			36	59	VIRACHOLAPURAM
			37	58	KODUNGAL
			38	47	ODIYATTUR
			39	46	KILVALAI (ANNIYUR)

		40	45	MELVALAI(I)
		41	49	ODUVANKUPPAM
		42	55	SENNAKUNAM
		43	44	KANDACHIPURAM
		44	32	ALAMBADI
		45	40	VIRANGIPURAM
		46	41	PUDUPPALAIYAM (VELANDAI)
		47	42	SENGAMEDU
		48	50	CHITTATTUR
		49	43	MADAVILAGAM
		50	48	KASBA KARANAI
		51	53	PERICHANUR
		52	54	CHITTERIPPATTU
		53	33	VEDALAM
		54	35	APPANANDAL
		55	34	PULRAMBATTU.SU
		56	60	ARKADU (NORTH)
		57	60	ARKADU (SOUTH)
		58	61	ARULAVADI
		59	31	TANIKKALAMBATTU
		60	28	KADAGANUR
		61	29	CHITTAMUR(VELANDAI)
		62	30	KINGILIVADI
IV. VIKRAVANDI	1.Sithalampattu	1	110	KALITTIRAMBATTU
		2	105	MUTTARAMPATTU
		3	106	NERKUNAM . V
		4	108	VALUDAVUR
		5	109	PAKKIRIPALAYAM
		6	107	KALINGAMALAI
		7	100	SESHANGANUR
		8	101	KURAMPALAIYAM
		9	99	VADANUR
		10	102	TIRUMANGALAM
		11	103	CHITTALAMBATTU
		12	104	KODUKKUR
		13	92	MADURAIPAKKAM
		14	93	MUNGILPATTU
		15	96	V.MATHUR
		16	98	KUMULAM
		17	97	MUDALIYARKUPPAM
		18	90	RADHAPURAM
		19	91	SEYYADU VINNAN
		20	95	PAGANDAI.V
		21	94	TENNAVARAYAMPATTU
		22	87	VAKKUR
		23	88	SIRUVALLIKULLAM
		24	89	VETTUKKADU
		25	83	TORAVI
		26	84	PANAIYAPURAM
		27	82	PANAPPAKKAM
		28	81	PAPPANAPATTU
		29	86	KAPPIYAMPULIUR

	30	85	(VADA)KUCHCHIPPALAIYAM
	31	113	AMMANANKUPPAM
	32	112	CHINNABABUSAMUDRAM
	33	111	PERIYABABUSAMUDRAM
2.Anniyur	34	22	TIRAKKUNAM
	35	23	PORUR
	36	46	SEMMEDU
	37	25	CHITTERI
	38	24	VELLERIPPATTU
	39	6	HANUMANTHAPURAM
	40	45	SIRUVALAI
	41	48	ARUMBULI
	42	50	ADANUR
	43	49	SURAPPATTU
	44	26	ELUSEMBON
	45	27	VIJAYANKUPPAM
	46	11	PANAMALAI (NORTH)
	47	11	PANAMALAI (SOUTH)
	48	21	ANNIYUR
	49	3	UDAIYANATTAM
	50	4	KULIRSUNAI
	51	7	VENGAMUR
	52	5	ATTIYUR (TIRUKKAI)
	53	47	KAKKANUR
	54	10	VELLAIYAMBATTU
	55	9	CHENNAPPANAYAKKAN PALAIYAM
	56	1	NALLAPPALAYAM
	57	2	KADAIYAM
	58	8	KARUVAKSHI
3.Kanjanur	59	41	KANJANUR
	60	42	VELIYANDAL
	61	28	MELKARANAI
	62	18	KALIYANAMPUNDI
	63	20	PERUNKALAMPUNDI
	64	13	SANGITAMANGALAM
	65	14	NANGATTUR
	66	43	KUNDALAPPULIYUR
	67	51	KASBAKARANAI
	68	52	PUNGUNAM
	69	12	SALAVANUR
	70	19	KANNANDAL
	71	54	VEMBI
	72	53	PUNDI
	73	44	KUNNATTUR-TANGAL
	74	29	NEMUR
	75	30	ARASALAPURAM
	76	40	KORALUR
	77	39	VENGAYAKKUPPAM
	78	31	MANDAGAPPATTU.E
	79	36	ICHCHANGUPPAM
	80	38	NARASINGANUR
	81	37	NANDIVADI

		82	56	ESALAM
		83	35	BRAHMADESAM
		84	57	ENNAYIARM
		85	34	TIRUNANDIPURAM
		86	58	PIDARIPPATTU
		87	17	MUTTATTUR
		88	33	SE. KUNNATTUR
		89	16	SE. PUDUR
		90	32	SE. KULAPPAKKAM
		91	15	NAGAR
		92	55	TENPER
		93	59	CHINNATAACHCHUR
	4.Vikravandi	94	67	KAYATTAR
		95	65	REDDIKUPPAM
		96	66	PILLAIYARKUPPAM
		97	68	AVADAIYARPATTU
		98	61	MELAKONDAI
		99	70	SATTANUR
		100	62	KONKARAMBUNDI
		101	71	KOTTIYAMPUNDI
		102	72	OLAGALA PUNDI
		103	60	AASUR (NORTH)
		104	60	AASUR (SOUTH)
		105	74	ORATTUR
		106	80	MUNDIYAMPAKKAM
		107	79	AYYUR AGARAM
		108	78	AYYANKOVILPATTU
		109	76	CHOLAGANUR
		110	75	TENNAMADEVI
		111	77	TIRUVAMATTUR
		112	73	TUMBUR
		113	69	VIKKIRAVANDI (EAST)
		114	69	VIKKIRAVANDI (WEST)
		115	63	V. SALAI(VIKKIRAVANDI)
		116	64	KUTTAMPUNDI
V. VANUR	1.Vanur	1	75	PATTANUR
		2	42	RAYAPUDUPPAKKAM
		3	43	TORUVAI
		4	71	AKASAMPATTU
		5	77	ACHARAMPATTU
		6	68	OTTAI
		7	69	VANUR
		8	70	PULICHAPALLAM
		9	76	TIRUCHITAMBALAM
		10	78	IRUMBAI
		11	72	KADAPPERIKUPPAM
		12	73	PERAMBAI
		13	37	MATHUR
		14	74	PUTHURAI

	2.Nemili	15	79	BOMMAYAPALAYAM
		16	80	KOTTAKUPPAM
		17	67	PUDUPPAKKAM(V)
		18	59	KURAKKENI
		19	53	PONNAMPUNDI
		20	57	AIVELI
		21	58	ILAIYANDAPATTU
		22	65	KONDALANKUPPAM
		23	64	THOLLAMUR
		24	56	IDAIYAPATTU
		25	62	SENGAMEDU
		26	63	KADAGAMBATTU
		27	61	TIRUVAKKARAI
		28	51	IRAIYUR
		29	52	NEMILI
		30	60	AMBULUKKAI
		31	55	POMBUR
	32	27	PERUMBAKKAM	
	33	50	KARASANUR	
	34	54	SIRUVAI	
	35	49	KUNNAM	
	36	48	ILVAMPATTU	
	37	47	SEMANGALAM	
	38	66	PARANGANI (V)	
	39	35	KALUPERUMBAKKAM	
	40	36	KOLUVARI	
	41	17	KARATTAI	
	42	18	ARUVADAI	
	43	10	KOMADIPPATTU	
	44	14	KILAPPAKKAM	
	45	13	CHITTANAPPAKKAM	
	46	12	KAYILMEDU	
	47	15	VANGARAM	
	48	38	NESAL	
	49	4	NALLAVUR	
	50	11	TALAIKANIKUPPAM	
	51	16	DEVANANDAL	
	52	6	ULAGAPURAM	
	53	9	UPPUVELUR	
	54	7	PARANGANI (T)	
	55	8	KUMALAMPATTU	
	56	5	PERAVUR	
	57	20	PUDUKKUPPAM	
	58	21	KUNJIMANGALAM	
	59	19	EDAICHERI	
	60	22	KILIYANUR (EAST)	
	61	22	KILIYANUR (WEST)	
	62	3	KONDAMUR	
	63	2	ARUVAPPAKKAM	
	64	24	SIRUVALUR(TEN)	

		65	26	PARIKKALPATTU	
		66	28	SIRUNAVUR	
		67	23	TERKUNAM	
		68	29	MURUKKAM	
		69	45	KATTARAMBAKKAM	
		70	32	TAILAPURAM	
		71	31	AGARAM (THEN)	
		72	30	KUTTAPPAKKAM(KIL)	
		73	1	KODIPPAKKAM (THEN)	
		74	25	ADANAPPATTU	
		75	44	OLUNDIYAPPATTU	
		76	41	RAYA OTTAI	
		77	40	KODUR	
		78	33	ANPAKKAM	
		79	46	KENIPPATTU (V)	
		80	34	VILVANATTAM	
		81	39	APPIRAMBATTU	
VI. TINDIVANAM	1.Mailam	1	154	MAILAM	
		2	141	CHENDUR	
		3	139	KOLLIYANKUNAM	
		4	138	NALLAMUR	
		5	140	VELANGAMPADI	
		6	157	KULAPPAKKAM(THEN)	
		7	160	THENALAPPAKKAM	
		8	153	KURALUR	
		9	159	KANNIYAM	
		10	158	TALUDALI	
		11	165	GANAPATHIPATTU	
		12	164	ANGANIKUPPAM	
		13	163	ATHIKUPPAM	
		14	161	KONAMANGALAM	
		15	156	VELIYANUR	
		16	155	ARIYANKUPPAM	
		17	152	PADIRIPPULIYUR	
		18	162	VEEDUR (E)	
		19	162	VEEDUR (W)	
		20	137	KALLAKULATTUR	
		2.Deevanur	21	15	DEEVANUR
			22	61	ASUR
			23	64	KOLLAR
			24	16	AGOOR
			25	17	NADUVANANDAL
			26	14	VILUKKAM
			27	57	PAMPUNDI
			28	58	KATTUSIVIRI
			29	59	SALAI
			30	60	PERADIKKUPPAM(MEL)
			31	10	TANIYAL
			32	100	VEMPUNDI
			33	101	MUTTIYUR
			34	99	PELAKUPPAM
			35	63	PERAMANDUR (EAST)

		36	63	PERAMANDUR (WEST)
		37	13	ILAMANGALAM
		38	12	MANNAMPUNDI
		39	66	PATTANAM
		40	65	VENMANIYATTUR
		41	11	PULIYANUR
	3.Rettanai	42	127	RATTANAI (EAST)
		43	127	RATTANAI (WEST)
		44	131	KUTTERIPPATTU
		45	123	KODIMA
		46	129	SOLIASOKKUNAM
		47	132	CHINNAVALAVANUR
		48	128	ALAGRAMAM (EAST)
		49	128	ALAGRAMAM (WEST)
		50	148	PERANI
		51	151	PALAPPATTU
		52	130	CHINNANERKUNAM
		53	142	NEDIMOZHIANUR
		54	144	NALLALAM.V
		55	145	PANCHALAM.V
		56	62	VENGANDUR
		57	124	PANDAMANGALAM
		58	122	KENIPPATTU. T
		59	147	SENDIYAMBAKKAM
		60	143	KOTTAMANGALAM (Se)
		61	146	PERIATHACHUR (SOUTH)
		62	146	PERIATHACHUR (NORTH)
		63	126	AVAIYARKUPPAM
		64	125	MUPPULI
		65	149	CHITTANI
		66	150	EZHAI
	4.Avanippur	67	94	SEVUR(KIL)
		68	88	SENALUR
		69	89	KILBOODERI
		70	39	KADAVAMBAKKAM
		71	37	KATTUPPUNJAI
		72	38	KALAVAY(VADA)
		73	86	MANDAPPERUMBAKKAM
		74	87	KUNNAPPAKKAM
		75	85	TENNAMPOONDI
		76	41	ANNAMBAKKAM
		77	40	AVANIPPUR
		78	81	SENDAMANGALAM
		79	90	MANNUR(KIL)
		80	84	VANDARAMPUNDI
		81	91	KARUPPUR
		82	83	NEMALI(KIL)
		83	92	PASAR(KIL)
		84	80	AKSHIPPAKKAM
		85	82	NARAMAGANI

		86	78	PANKOLATTUR
		87	79	PANAIYUR
	5.Olakkur	88	34	PADIRI
		89	33	KUTTIKKULATTUR
		90	36	ONGUR
		91	42	KAMBUR
		92	35	KARIKKAMBATTU
		93	44	NALLATTUR
		94	76	PALLIPPAKKAM
		95	43	NANGUNAM
		96	95	NOLAMBUR
		97	77	EPPAKKAM
		98	93	ANDAPPATTU
		99	31	OLAKKUR(MELPADI)
		100	32	OLAKKUR(KILPADI)
		101	45	S.KADUR
		102	75	ADANUR(KIL)
		103	74	MANGALAM
		104	72	GUDALUR(KIL)
		105	73	ICHCHERI
	6.Vadasiruvalur	106	56	URAL
		107	1	MAMBAKKAM
		108	2	SEMBAKKAM
		109	3	KONALUR
		110	8	PUTTANANDAL
		111	6	VELLIMEDU
		112	50	MELPAKKAM
		113	69	SATTANUR
		114	68	CHITTERIPPATTU
		115	25	ADANUR(MEL)
		116	26	AMMANAMBAKKAM
		117	9	SIRUVALUR(VADA)
		118	19	NAGAVARAM
		119	22	DHADHAPURAM
		120	23	SINGANIKUPPAM
		121	24	MALAIYANUR(KIL)
		122	29	VAIRAPURAM
		123	30	TENGAPAKKAM
		124	27	KODIAM
		125	55	KARUVAPAKKAM
		126	54	KIRANDIPURAM
		127	52	PERAPPERI
		128	53	VADAMPUNDI
		129	5	ATHIPPAKKAM
		130	7	NEDUNTHONDI
		131	4	SIVIRI(MEL)
		132	70	PANCHALAM. T
		133	71	PETTAI(MEL)
		134	46	SARAM
		135	51	NEYKUPPI
		136	28	PULIYUR
		137	21	MAVILANGAI(KIL)
		138	20	MAVILANGAI(MEL)

		139	18	KALPAKKAM
		140	47	PURANGARAI
		141	49	EVALLUR
		142	48	KARANAI(KIL)
	7.Tindivanam	143	117	OMANDUR
		144	106	IRAIYANUR
		145	105	KARNAVUR
		146	104	JAKKAMPETTAI
		147	98	SALAVADI
		148	102	SINGANUR
		149	120	KALAVAY(THEN)
		150	103	PASIYAR(THEN)
		151	121	AVANAMPATTU
		152	133	IDAIYALAM(KIL)
		153	119	ANNAMPUTTUR
		154	118	VARAGUPPATTU
		155	135	VENGAI
		156	134	PERADIKKUPPAM(KIL)
		157	136	SITHAMUR(KIL)
		158	96	KATTALAI
		159	112	JANAKIPETTAI
		160	110	ENDIYUR
		161	111	GURUVAMMAPETTAI
		162	116	MOLASUR
		163	115	KOVADI
		164	97	VITALAPURAM
		165	114	NERKUNAM(THEN)
		166	113	ILAVALAPPAKKAM
		167	109	ATTUR
		168	107	MAANUR
		169	67	TINDIVANAM
		170	169	AVARAIPPAKKAM
		171	168	ROSHANAI
		172	167	KAVERIPPAKKAM
		173	108	ALAPPAKKAM(VADA)
		174	166	GIDANGAL
VII. GINGEE	1.Melolakkur	1	23	AGALUR
		2	13	MUKKUNAM
		3	9	DAMANUR
		4	8	CHINNAGARAM
		5	32	ARUGAVUR
		6	37	PANAPPAKKAM
		7	15	ICHCHUR
		8	29	ETHANEMELI
		9	20	KARIYAMANGALAM
		10	19	CHELLAPIRATTI
		11	2	KANDAMANALLUR
		12	3	IRUMBULI
		13	1	UDAIYANTANGAL
		14	24	AVIYUR
		15	41	VIRPATTU

		16	22	SETHUVAYANALLUR
		17	33	PALLIKULAM
		18	34	KUTTAPPAKKAM (MEL)
		19	35	INDIRISANKUPPAM
		20	16	ILLODU
		21	18	MAHADEVIMANGALAM
		22	17	SANDISAKSHI
		23	4	KALLAPPULIYUR
		24	30	MELATTIPPAKKAM
		25	31	EADAIMALAI
		26	7	PENNAGAR
		27	14	KARUNGULI
		28	27	VIRANAMUR
		29	6	CHOLANGUNAM
		30	5	PERUMPUNDI
		31	26	PONDAI
		32	25	NANGIYANANDAL
		33	44	KALAVAY (MEL)
		34	21	NEKANUR
		35	28	NIRPERUTTAGARAM
		36	38	ANANGUR
		37	40	PUTTUR(VADA)
		38	39	KORAVANANDAL
		39	10	TONDUR
		40	11	BUDERI
		41	12	MEL OLAKKUR
	2.Vallam	42	147	THIRUVAMBATTU
		43	156	KILMAMBATTU
		44	146	VADATARAM
		45	144	MELSEVUR (EAST)
		46	144	MELSEVUR (WEST)
		47	157	KALLADIKUPPAM
		48	160	NAGANDUR
		49	159	MARUR
		50	161	DALAVALAPPATTU
		51	158	VAILAMUR (KIL)
		52	155	ERRAMBATTU
		53	143	KONGARAPPATTU
		54	162	PUTTUR(THEN)
		55	163	AMUR
		56	164	PERAMPATTU
		57	137	MODAIYUR (WEST)
		58	137	MODAIYUR (EAST)
		59	149	DALAVANUR
		60	150	KALLALIPPATTU
		61	153	ANILADI
		62	151	VAUVALKUNRAM
		63	152	GUDALUR(MEL)
		64	154	VILVAMADEVI
		65	134	CHITTAMUR (MEL)

		66	36	MELATTUR
		67	140	KAMMANDUR
		68	141	KILAIYUR
		69	142	MANIYAMPATTU
		70	136	VALLAM
		71	135	MARUDERI
		72	139	TAIYUR
		73	145	PAPPAMBADI(KIL)
		74	125	SORATTUR
		75	124	KAPPAI
		76	43	PERUMPUGAI
		77	42	ANATTUR
		78	128	NANGILIKONDAN
		79	129	VADAVANUR
		80	130	SERVILAGAM
		81	131	KADAMBUR
		82	132	KALAIYUR
		83	133	NATTARMANGALAM
		84	126	KURINJIPPAI
		85	138	TUDUPPAKKAM
		86	127	RAJAMPULIYUR
	3.Sathiyamangalam	87	97	PADIPPALLAM
		88	98	SENNALUR
		89	95	DEVADANAMPETTAI
		90	96	PERIYAMUR
		91	71	PAPPAMBADI (MEL)
		92	88	MALAVANTANGAL
		93	87	MALLIRISANKUPPAM
		94	79	MADAPPUNDI
		95	81	NAGALAMBATTU
		96	80	KANJUR
		97	82	ULIYAMBATTU
		98	91	TUTTIPPATTU
		99	89	PONNANKUPPAM
		100	93	GANGAVARAM
		101	92	KANAKKANKUPPAM
		102	78	NALLANPILLAIPETRAL
		103	76	KATTUCHITTAMUR
		104	75	TADANKUPPAM
		105	62	PERUNGAPPUR
		106	61	PASUMALAITANGAL
		107	64	ALAMPUNDI
		108	63	BHARATANTANGAL
		109	84	THADAKAM
		110	85	POTTUVAI
		111	86	PALAVALAM
		112	83	SETTAVARAI
		113	57	ODIYATTUR
		114	58	CHINNAPONNANPUNDI
		115	65	SATYAMANGALAM
		116	60	NAYAMPADI
		117	59	MANALAADI
		118	66	SORATTUPPERIYANKUPPAM

		119	77	PAKKAM
		120	67	PUDUPPALAIYAM
		121	72	PETTAI(GINGEE)
		122	73	PUTTAGARAM
		123	68	PULIPPATTU
		124	74	KAMAGARAM
		125	70	SEMMEDU
		126	69	VIRAMANALLUR
		127	94	TANDAVASAMUDRAM
	4.Gingee	128	114	ANANTAPURAM
		129	113	KILMALAI
		130	90	CHITTARASUR
		131	112	KONALUR
		132	115	PULIVANDI
		133	111	ANAIYERI
		134	110	MULLUR
		135	107	ATTIYUR
		136	106	THACHCHAMBATTU
		137	108	VARIKKAL
		138	109	ARUNGUNAM (MEL)
		139	116	MATHUR TIRUKKAI
		140	118	ODDAMBATTU
		141	120	TIRUVADIKKUNNAM
		142	119	MATTAPPARAI
		143	121	TEN PUDUPPATTU
		144	122	PALAPPATTU
		145	148	KOMMEDU
		146	123	MAVATTAMBADI
		147	53	IDAIYALAM (MEL)
		148	54	JAYANKONDAN
		149	105	SITTAMPUNDI
		150	99	SIRUNAMPUNDI
		151	56	KONAI
		152	100	APPAMBATTU
		153	50	PONPATTI
		154	52	ANJANCHERI
		155	51	URANITTANGAL
		156	46	SIRUKADAMBUR
		157	47	KRISHNAPURAM
		158	103	JAMBODI
		159	102	MEENAMBUR
		160	101	KAVARAI
		161	104	KADAGAMPUNDI
		162	45	SINGAVARAM
		163	48	GINGEE
		164	49	SAKKARAPURAM
		165	55	NARASINGARAYANPETTAI
		166	117	KARAI

VIII. Melmalayanur	1.Avalurpettai	1	1	ETHAPATTU	
		2	2	VAILAMUR (MEL)	
		3	14	KODAMBADI	
		4	15	VADUGAPOONDI	
		5	13	PARAIYAMPATTU	
		6	12	TALANKUNNAM	
		7	20	KAPPALAMBADI	
		8	23	KOTTAIPPUNDI	
		9	22	SINDIPPATTU	
		10	11	NARANAMANGALAM	
		11	10	UNNAMANDAL	
		12	9	SEVALAMBADI (MEL)	
		13	3	TEPPIRAMBATTU	
		14	4	NANDIPURAM	
		15	7	CHINNANOLAMBAI	
		16	6	PERIYANOLAMBAI	
		17	5	PARUTHIPURAM	
		18	8	EYYIL	
		19	24	SANGILIKKUPPAM	
		20	25	PARAIYANTANGAL	
		21	26	PAZHAMPOONDI	
		22	17	AVALURPET	
		23	16	KADAPPANANDAL	
		24	18	KOVILPURAIYUR	
		25	19	KUNDHALAMPATTU	
		2. Sathampadi	26	50	SATHAMPADI
			27	53	SIRUDALAIPUNDI
			28	54	VALATTI
			29	55	KANNALAM
			30	74	MANNUR(MEL)
			31	73	TURINJIPPUNDI
			32	75	PORKUNRAM
			33	47	ANNAMANGALAM
			34	46	SATTANANDAL
			35	48	DEVANUR
			36	43	GANGAPURAM
			37	44	CHITTERI
			38	45	SAMATTANKUPPAM
			39	30	KUDUVAMPUNDI
			40	28	ARKKAMPUNDI
			41	27	SINDAGAMPUNDI
			42	31	NEMALI (MEL)
			43	29	KILAVANPUNDI
			44	49	VADAVETTI
			45	41	KARANAI (MEL)
			46	42	SEVALAMBADI (KIL)
			47	38	MARAKKONAM
			48	32	PINNANUR
			49	33	KAMMANTANGAL
			50	39	PAPPANTANGAL
			51	37	PERUVALUR
			52	40	CHOKKAPALAM

		53	34	DEVANDAVADI
		54	36	MODIPPATTU
		55	35	KAIVIDANTANGAL
	3.Melmalayanur	56	52	MALAIYANUR (MEL)
		57	51	KODUDUKKANKUPPAM
		58	58	TAYANUR
		59	59	MANANDAL
		60	67	SIYAPPUNDI
		61	60	ATTIPPATTU
		62	61	KULAPPALUR
		63	68	TORAPPADI
		64	57	MEL MAMBATTU
		65	66	MEL PUDUPPATTU
		66	70	VADAPALAI
		67	64	THENPALAI
		68	62	KALATTAMBATTU
		69	65	ARUNGANAM(MEL)
		70	63	CHOKKANANDAL
		71	69	IYYAKKUNRAM
		72	72	EMBALAM
		73	56	SATTAPPUTTUR
		74	71	SEVALAPURAI (NORTH)
		75	71	SEVALAPURAI (SOUTH)
		76	79	MELCHERI
		77	76	KADALI
		78	77	MAVANANDAL
		79	78	VANAKKAMBADI
		80	21	NOCHCHILUR
IX. MARAKKANAM	1.Siruvadi	1	30	MUNNUR (SOUTH)
		2	30	MUNNUR (NORTH)
		3	21	KURUR
		4	22	VAIDAPAKKAM
		5	28	VEPPERI
		6	37	OMIPPER
		7	26	VADAKODIPPAKKAM
		8	32	ADAVALLIKUTTAN
		9	36	ADASAL
		10	31	SORAPPATTU
		11	27	SIRUVADI
		12	34	MURUKKERI
		13	38	NADUKKUPPAM (EAST)
		14	38	NADUKKUPPAM (WEST)
		15	35	KULATTUR
		16	33	SATTAMANGALAM
		17	29	SINGANANDAL
		18	3	NALLUR
		19	2	PANTADU
		20	4	NERKUNAM(VADA)
		21	20	ALANGUPPAM
		22	1	NAGALPAKKAM
		23	24	RAYANALLUR
		24	23	NAGAR

	2.Brammadesam	25	8	NALMUKKAL	
		26	16	ALAGIYAPAKKAM	
		27	17	CHOKKANTANGAL	
		28	10	ARUNGUNAM(KIL)	
		29	9	KULAPPAKKAM(VADA)	
		30	15	NALLALAM. T	
		31	12	PALAMUKKAL	
		32	18	BRAMMADESAM	
		33	11	PERUMUKKAL	
		34	14	SIVIRI(KIL)	
		35	13	TENNERI	
		36	5	ENDUR	
		37	7	ARIYANTANGAL	
		38	6	MADAVANTANGAL	
		39	19	VANNIPPER	
		3.Marakkanam	40	52	ANUMANDAI
			41	54	CHETTIKUPPAM
			42	53	SEYYANKUPPAM
			43	55	KOONIMEDU
	44		56	PUTHUPPATTU(KIL)	
	45		25	ASAPPUR	
	46		39	ALATTUR	
	47		40	KURUMBARAM	
	48		41	KANTHADU (E)	
	49		41	KANTHADU (W)	
	50		46	TIRUKKANUR	
	51		45	KESAVANAYAKKENPALAIYAM	
	52		44	PUDUPPAKKAM. M	
	53		47	URANI	
	54		48	ALAPPAKKAM	
	55		43	AGARAM(VADA)	
	56		50	PANICHCHAMEDU	
	57		49	ATCHIKADU	
	58		51	PETTAI(KIL)	
	59		42	MARAKKANAM (SOUTH)	
	60		42	MARAKKANAM (NORTH)	

//p.t.o.//

ABSTRACT

Name of the District	Name of the Division	Name of Taluk	No. of Firka	No. of Revenue Villages
VILUPPURAM	VILUPPURAM	1) VILUPPURAM**	4	123
		2) THIRUVENNAINALLUR (new)	3	70
		3) KANDACHIPURAM	2	62
		4) VIKRAVANDI	4	116
		5) VANUR	4	81
	TINDIVANAM	6) TINDIVANAM	7	174
		7) GINGEE	4	166
		8) MELMALAYANUR	3	80
		9) MARAKKANAM	3	60
		Total	34	932

**** Sittalingamadam Firka, Thiruvonnainallur Firka Detached from Thirukovilur Taluk, Aarasur Firka Detached from Ulundurpet Taluk and added to Viluppuram Taluk.**

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

//True Copy//

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12/11/19
Section Officer

ANNEXURE - XI

G.O.(Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management Department, dated 12.11.2019

Taluk-wise list of Villages in the Kallakurichi new District

Name of the Taluk	Name of the Firka	Sl. No.	Village No.	Name of the Village		
I. KALLAKURICHI	1. Indili	1	43	INDILI		
		2	47	PORPADAKURICHCHI		
		3	37	TACHCHUR		
		4	36	VILAMBAR		
		5	35	MALAIKOTHALAM		
		6	48	LACHCHIYAM		
		7	49	KATTANANDAL		
		8	50	TORASALUR(THEN)		
		9	51	VANAVARATTI		
		10	45	MELUR		
		11	46	ERAVAR		
		12	44	KILPUNDI		
		13	42	VINAITIRTAPURAM		
		14	38	OLAGAMKATHAN		
		15	39	BANGARAM		
		16	40	NAMASIVAYAPURAM		
		17	41	KANIYAMUR		
		18	73	RAYARPALAIYAM		
		19	72	PETHANUR		
		20	74	ESANDHAI		
		21	71	SIRUVATTUR		
		22	77	PUKKIRAVARI		
		23	70	VARADAPPANUR		
		24	75	OLAGIYANALLUR		
		25	76	NATTARMANGALAM(I)		
		2. Thiyagathurgam	26	15	VIRACHOLAPURAM (EAST)	
				27	15	VIRACHOLAPURAM (WEST)
				28	16	PRIDIVIMANGALAM
				29	17	TORASALUR (VADA)
				30	18	ANDIYUR
				31	19	KUNNIYUR
				32	20	UDAIYAMAMPATTU
				33	21	PERIYAMAMBATTU
				34	25	MELVIZHI
				35	26	TENNERIKUPPAM
				36	27	TIMMALAI
				37	28	VALAVANDANKUPPAM
				38	24	CHINNAMAMBATTU
				39	30	TIYAGAI
				40	29	SIRUVAL
				41	22	PUKKULAM

//p.t.o.//

		42	23	VILAKKUR
		43	31	CHITTALUR
		44	59	VENGAIVADI
		45	65	SOMANATHAPURAM
		46	60	KUDIYANALLUR
		47	62	SIRUNAGALUR
		48	61	PORAIYUR
	3. Nagalur	49	57	NAGALUR
		50	58	VADAPUNDI
		51	67	KANDACHCHIMANGALAM
		52	55	VIRUGAVUR
		53	33	MUDIYANUR
		54	32	MADAM
		55	34	KURUR (NORTH)
		56	34	KURUR (SOUTH)
		57	54	KANANGUR
		58	52	SATTANUR
		59	53	CHITTERI
		60	56	PORASAKKURICHCHI
		61	69	OGAIYUR.SU
		62	79	PERUMANGALAM
		63	78	SIRUMANGALAM
		64	80	KILNARIYAPPANUR
		65	85	KONGARAYAPALAIYAM
		66	68	VELAKKURICHCHI
		67	86	KUTTAKUDI
		68	66	UDAIYANACHCHI
		69	83	EYANUR
		70	84	VARANJARAM
		71	64	NINNAIYUR
		72	63	KOTTAIYUR
		73	89	CHITTATTUR
		74	88	GURUPIDAPURAM
		75	90	KOONDALUR
		76	87	ERANJI
		77	91	KACHCHAKUDI
		78	82	ASAKALATTUR
		79	81	MAGARUR
	4. Kallakurichi	80	1	NALLATTUR
		81	2	MATTIGAIKURICHCHI
		82	5	KARANUR
		83	4	KUDIRAICHCHANDAL
		84	6	EMAPPER
		85	7	KALLAKURICHI
		86	8	MAMANANDAL.KA
		87	9	SIRUVANGUR
		88	10	PERUVANGUR
		89	11	NILAMANGALAM
		90	12	KIRANUR(THEN)

		91	13	NIRAIMATHI
		92	14	MAADUR
		93	3	SADAIYAMPATTU
II.SANKARAPURAM	1.Vadaponparappi	1	29	LAKKINAYAKKANPATTI
		2	26	RAVATTANALLUR
		3	28	RANGAPPANUR
		4	27	PUDUPPATTU
		5	39	MANGALAM
		6	40	IRUDAIYAMBATTU
		7	45	ADANUR
		8	36	MUNGILTURAIPPATTU
		9	38	PORASAPPATTU
		10	37	PORUVALLUR
		11	43	ARULAMBADI
		12	41	OLAGALAPPADI
		13	42	PONPARAPPI(VADA)
		14	34	VADAKIRANUR
		15	31	BRAHMAKUNDAM
		16	32	RAYASAMUDRAM
		17	35	SIRUVALLUR(MEL)
		18	33	MANALUR
		19	30	PAVUNJIPPATTU
		20	69	PAKKAM
		21	70	KADUVANUR
		22	67	TOLUVANTANGAL
		23	68	KANANKADU
		24	4	MOOLADADU
		25	61	PERIYAKOLLIYUR
		26	60	CHINNAKOLLIYUR
		27	65	ARIYALUR
		28	66	ATTIYUR
		29	50	JAMBADAI
		30	51	TIRUVARANGAM
		31	47	ARKKAVADI
		32	46	SUTTAMALAI
		33	49	SRIPADANALLUR
		34	48	ARUMBARAMBATTU
		35	44	VADAMAMANDUR
		36	52	SU.KALLIPPADI
		37	54	SIRPANANDAL
		38	59	EDUTTANUR
		39	55	SIRUPANAIYUR
		40	53	MANIYANDAL
		41	56	KADAMBUR
		42	58	ODIYANDAL
		43	57	MARUR
		44	62	NAGALKUDI
		45	63	VANAPURAM

	3. Rishivandiyam	46	144	RISHIVANDIYAM	
		47	145	VENGALAM	
		48	149	MUTTIYAM	
		49	150	MANDAGAPPADI	
		50	146	MUNIVALAI	
		51	148	ALLIYABATH	
		52	147	PIRAVADAIYAMBATTU	
		53	138	KALAIYANALLUR	
		54	139	PILAMEDU	
		55	132	SULANKURICHCHI	
		56	137	PALLAGACHCHERI	
		57	104	PALAIYASIRUVANGUR	
		58	135	PALLIPPATTU	
		59	136	VALANANDAL	
		60	133	CHITTERIPPATTU	
		61	97	YAL	
		62	95	MAIYANUR	
		63	98	PORPPALAMPATTU	
		64	96	PERIYA PAGANDAI	
		65	64	ENDAL	
		66	100	LA.GUDALUR	
		67	99	AVIRIYUR	
		68	101	KILPADI	
		69	134	CHITTAL	
		70	140	PERAL	
		71	141	SATTAPUTTUR	
		72	142	PAVANDUR	
		73	103	MELPALANGUR	
		74	102	NUROLAI	
		75	143	PASAR	
		4. Alathur	76	112	SESHASAMUDRAM
			77	111	NEDUMANUR
			78	119	ALATTUR
			79	127	ARIYAPERUMANUR
			80	129	TANDALAI (NORTH)
			81	129	TANDALAI (SOUTH)
			82	131	AGARAKOTTALAM
			83	130	ANAICKARAIKOTTALAM
			84	128	VANIYANDAL
			85	108	RAMRAJAPURAM
			86	107	PALAIYANUR
			87	109	MANJAPUTTUR
			88	110	CHETTIYANDAL (VADA)
			89	106	VALAIYAMBATTU
			90	115	MELAPATTU
			91	116	KILAPATTU
			92	117	PARAMANATTAM
			93	118	NEYVANATTAM

		94	105	KALLERIKUPPAM
		95	124	MOKUR
		96	125	SOMANDARKUDI
		97	126	M.VANNANJUR
		98	123	KA.ALAMBALAM
		99	122	SEMBADAKURICHCHI
		100	121	POMBARAPPATTU
		101	120	TIRUKKANANGUR
		102	114	MURARBATH
		103	113	CHOLAMBATTU
	5. Sankarapuram	104	81	SANKARAPURAM
		105	80	KATTUVANNANJUR
		106	84	DEVAPANDALAM
		107	85	A.PANDALAM
		108	86	Su.KULATTUR
		109	88	ARUR
		110	89	VARAGUR
		111	91	TIMMANANDAL
		112	90	CHELLAKKAKUPPAM
		113	93	VIRIYUR
		114	94	ARASARAMBATTU
		115	92	KIDANGUDAIYAMBATTU
		116	23	MALLAPURAM
		117	25	PUTTIRAMBATTU
		118	24	SITTANTANGAL
		119	73	MUKKANUR
		120	72	OLAGADAIYAMPATTU
		121	71	SIVAPURAM
		122	83	SOWNDARVALLIPALAIYAM
		123	74	URANGANI
		124	82	TYAGARAJAPURAM
		125	75	PUTTAI
		126	79	SEMBARAMBATTU
		127	78	POYKKUNAM
		128	76	ARASAMBATTU
		129	77	KOSAPPADI
		130	87	SIRUVALLUR(VADA)
		131	21	PACHERRI
		132	20	PUDUPALAPATTU
		133	19	KALLIPATTU
III.CHINNASALEM	1.Vadakkananthal	1	10	EDUTTAVAINATTAM
		2	11	CHELLAMBATTU
		3	13	MANMALAI
		4	12	KARADICHITTUR (NORTH)
		5	12	KARADICHITTUR (SOUTH)
		6	14	THAVADIPATU
		7	15	MADAVACHCHERI (NORTH)
		8	15	MADAVACHCHERI (SOUTH)
		9	16	PALARAMBATTU

		10	17	MATTUR
		11	18	VADAKKANANDAL (EAST)
		12	18	VADAKKANANDAL (WEST)
		13	20	KACHCHIRAYAPALAYAM
		14	21	PARIGAM
		15	19	ERUVAYPATTANAM
		16	29	MALLIYAMPADI
		17	30	POTTIYAM
	2.Nayinarpalayam	18	69	NAYINARPALAIYAM
		19	76	ANUMANANDAL
		20	77	KILKUPPAM
		21	85	MAMANTHUR.V
		22	84	KARUNDALAKURICHCHI
		23	78	KRISHNAPURAM (VRIDDHACHALAM)
		24	79	ALAMBALAM (VIRDDHACHALAM)
		25	80	KURAL
		26	66	KALASAMUDRAM
		27	65	DAGAMTIRTTAPURAM
		28	81	PAKKAMBADI
		29	70	SIRUVALLUR(THEN)
		30	75	SEMBAKURICHCHI
		31	64	TOTTAPPADI
		32	68	PETTASAMUDRAM
		33	67	DATTADRIPURAM
		34	74	KARUNGULI
		35	71	AMMAKALATTUR
		36	72	IRIYUR
		37	73	NALLASEVIPURAM
		38	82	KOOGAIYUR
		39	83	VEERABAYANGARAM
	3.Chinnasalem	40	41	KADATTUR
		41	43	TENGIYANATTAM
		42	44	ELIYATTUR
		43	45	PAYITTANDURAI
		44	46	TOTTIYAM
		45	47	CHETTIYANDAL(THEN)
		46	53	VETTIPERUMALAGARAM
		47	52	MARAVANATTAM
		48	42	PADARAMPALLAM(E)
		49	60	RAYAPPANUR
		50	59	MELNARIYAPPANUR
		51	58	PONPARAPPI(THEN)
		52	48	TAKARAI
		53	49	KALLANATTAM
		54	51	PANDIYANKUPPAM
		55	50	TIMMAPURAM
		56	56	ILAVADI

		57	57	PUSAPPADI	
		58	62	AMMAIYAGARAM	
		59	55	MUNGILPADI	
		60	63	PUNDI	
		61	61	(AGRAHARA)VASUDEVANUR	
		62	54	CHINNASLAM (NORTH)	
		63	54	CHINNASLAM (SOUTH)	
IV. KALRAYAN HILLS (New)	1. Kalrayan Hills	1	9	KILAKKADU	
		2	11	KALLIPPRAI	
		3	10	GUDARAM	
		4	14	MELNILAVUR	
		5	13	KIL NILAVUR	
		6	12	VILVATHI	
		7	8	PERUMALNATTAM	
		8	2	CHERIYAPATTU	
		9	3	KURUMBALUR	
		10	1	ALANUR	
		11	5	VAZHAIKUZHI	
		12	6	VANJIKKUZHI	
		13	7	SIRUKKALUR	
		14	15	VENGADU	
		15	17	MOTTAIYANUR	
		16	22	PERUMPUR	
		17	18	VELARIKKADU	
		18	16	ERUKKAMBATTU	
		2. Vellimalai	19	2	MANIYARPALAIYAM
			20	1	ARAVANKADU
			21	3	MELATHUKUZHI
			22	4	KELATHUKUZHI
			23	5	ENNADU
			24	6	KARIYALUR
			25	7	MAVADIPPATTU
			26	8	NOCHIMEDU
			27	9	KARUVELAMPADI
			28	22	KONDIYANATTAM
			29	23	VALAPPADI (MEL)
			30	24	VELLIMALAI
			31	28	KANDIKKOLLAI
			32	27	VANNIYUR
			33	26	ARAMPUNDI
			34	25	MOZHIPATTU
			35	36	VARAM
			36	35	UPPUR
			37	34	ERUKKAMBATTU
			38	33	VANDAGAPPADI
			39	37	TORANGUR
			40	32	TODARIPPATTU (MEL)
			41	38	EZHUTHUR

		42	31	MUNDIYUR
		43	40	NARANAPPATTI
		44	39	MEL PARACHCHERI
V. TIRUKOILUR	1.Tiruppalapandal	1	31	TIRUPPALAPANDAL
		2	33	TURINJIPPATTU
		3	34	PARADAPATTU
		4	40	PONNIYANDAL
		5	39	MEYYUR(PONNIYANDAL)
		6	41	KOMALUR
		7	25	MUDIYANUR
		8	32	PUMARI
		9	45	CHOLAVANDIPURAM
		10	26	TAKADI
		11	28	KUVANUR
		12	27	MELARIPPATTU
		13	42	PANAPPADI
		14	44	KONAKKALAVADI
		15	43	TATTANUR
		16	47	TIMMICHCHUR
		17	46	PADIYANDAL
		18	48	KOLAPPARAI
		19	49	NEDUMUDAIYAN
		20	37	MADAMPUNDI
		21	29	ARUDANGUDI
		22	38	IRUMBALAKKURICHCHI
		23	30	IDAIYUR
		24	35	NARIYANDAL
		25	36	DEVIYANDAL
	2.Tirukoilur	26	53	TIRUKKOVILUR (NORTH)
		27	52	KILAIYUR
		28	53	TIRUKKOVILUR (SOUTH)
		29	54	AVIYUR
		30	50	KARADI
		31	51	KIRANUR (TIRUKKOVILUR)
		32	59	THAZHANUR (MEL)
		33	60	KANAKANANDAL
		34	61	SIVANARTANGAL
		35	62	TANAKANANDAL
		36	58	THAZHANUR (KIL)
		37	63	VENMAR
		38	57	ARUMBAKKAM
		39	65	ARIYUR
		40	66	SENGANANKOLLAI
		41	73	ERAVALAM
		42	64	VENGUR(I)
		43	69	ALUR
		44	70	MOGALAR
		45	67	MEMALUR
		46	68	KADIYAR

	3.Manalurpettai	47	71	PALANGUR
		48	72	PERIYANUR
		49	55	DEVIYAGARAM
		50	56	KACHIKUVACHAN
		51	11	MANALURPETTAI
		52	10	CHITTAPATTANAM
		53	13	SANGIYAM
		54	12	CHITTAMUR (JA)
		55	1	MELANDAL
		56	2	KANGIYANUR
		57	3	PALLICHCHANDAL
		58	17	ATTIPPAKKAM (TIRUKKOVILUR)
		59	6	ATTIYANDAL
		60	8	JAMBAI
		61	5	MURUKKAMBADI
		62	9	CHELLANKUPPAM
		63	7	DEVARADIYARKUPPAM
		64	15	KOLUNDIRAMBATTU
		65	16	NEDUNGAMBATTU
		66	18	SADAIKATTI
		67	19	PUTTAGARAM
		68	4	KONGANAMUR
		69	14	SORAYAPPATTU
		70	24	KALUMALAM
71	23	KOTTAGAM		
72	22	VELANDAI		
73	20	KULADEEPAMANGALAM		
74	21	AGASTYARMOOLAI		
V.ULUNDURPET	1.Eraiur	1	1	KATTU IDAIYAR
		2	7	PERIYAKURUKKAI
		3	15	ERAIYUR
		4	4	DHANAM
		5	5	PALLAVADI
		6	6	MAYILADUNTANGAL
		7	10	KUVADU
		8	11	TENKUNAM
		9	13	NEYVANAI
		10	12	EDALAVADI
		11	18	ADAIYUR
		12	17	PILLAIYARPALAIYAM
		13	92	NATTAMUR
		14	91	ATTIPPAKKAM (ELAVANASUR). A
		15	22	SIKKADU
		16	24	PALANGUNAM
		17	23	SIRUNAGALUR
		18	16	KUNJARAM
		19	19	POONDI

		20	20	SIDEVI
		21	21	KULATTUR(ELAVANASUR)
		22	2	KATTUSELLUR
		23	3	KOMMASAMUDRAM
		24	8	KUTTANUR
		25	9	ELLAIGRAMAM
		26	14	KURUMBUR (VADA)
	2.Elavanasurkottai	27	33	PIDAGAM
		28	34	PUTTUR(ELAVANASUR)
		29	30	ANGANUR
		30	29	SEMBATTAMALAIYANUR
		31	43	MALAIYANUR(PULLUR)
		32	42	NONAIYAVADI
		33	47	PARINDAL
		34	48	SIYYAMANGALAM
		35	36	SALAPPAKKAM
		36	37	PINNALAVADI
		37	38	ALANGIRI
		38	35	SUNDARAVANDI
		39	39	SEMBIYAMADEV
		40	40	CHETTIYANDAL
		41	41	MANGALAM (PARAMESWARI)
		42	50	TIRUPPAYAR
		43	49	PUDUKKALANI
		44	45	PUTTAMANGALAM
		45	46	NEDUMANUR
		46	44	SIRUVATTUR
		47	31	EMAM
		48	32	SIRUPAKKAM
		49	26	POGAPPATTI
		50	27	VANNAKAPPADI
		51	25	VIRAMANGALAM
		52	28	ARUMBALAVADI
	3.Kalamaru Dur	53	83	KALAMARUDUR
		54	84	ATTUR
		55	82	ADANUR
		56	88	MA.KUNNATTUR
		57	93	PUVANUR
		58	94	VADA MAMBAKKAM
		59	96	DAMAL
		60	97	PUTTANANDAL
		61	95	SIKKAMBATTU
		62	103	PERIYASEVALAI
		63	101	AMUR
		64	102	TOLANGAMBATTU
		65	104	SARAVANAMBAKKAM
		66	105	KOTTANUR
		67	87	NANNARAM

		68	86	TIRUNIRANKONRAI
		69	85	VELUR
		70	90	KILIYUR
		71	89	RAGHUNATHAPURAM
		72	99	KULATTUR(TIRUKKOVILUR)
		73	98	KONDASAMUDRAM
		74	100	ODDANANDAL
	4.Sengurichi	75	161	ANDIKKULI
		76	160	VIJAYANKUPPAM
		77	164	ARINATTAM
		78	163	KUTTADI
		79	174	ODAPPANKUPPAM
		80	175	ELAVATHADY
		81	170	MATTIGAI
		82	171	VANAMBATTU
		83	172	KALLAMEDU
		84	166	MAMBAKKAM(PULLUR)
		85	139	ORATTUR (T)
		86	138	KILLANUR(PADUR)
		87	137	PERUMBATTU
		88	165	SENGURICHCHI
		89	65	SEMMANANGUR
		90	64	NAGAR
		91	140	PADUR
		92	169	KALLAKKURICHI. KU
		93	173	SENDANADU
		94	167	MADIYANUR
		95	168	ILUPPAIYUR
	5.Ulundurpet	96	56	PULLUR
		97	53	EDAIKKAL
		98	52	MALAVARAYANUR (ELAVANASUR)
		99	57	KATTUNEMILI
		100	58	ARASAMPUNDI
		101	59	KURUMBUR(A)
		102	55	PALI
		103	54	SATTANUR. A (ELAVANASUR)
		104	71	KANAIYAR
		105	72	KUMARAMANGALAM (ELAVANASUR)
		106	79	NEMALI (U)
		107	78	SELLUR (U)
		108	77	KALAVANUR
		109	51	ASANUR
		110	74	KONALAVADI (PULLUR)
		111	61	MEPPULIYUR
		112	62	KILLANUR(PULLUR)
		113	60	NACHCHIYARPETTAI

		114	63	ULUNDUR
		115	66	KIRANUR (ULUNDURPET)
		116	80	KAMABATTU
		117	81	PACHAPALAIYAM
		118	75	PANDUR
		119	76	ARALI
		120	69	OLAIYANUR
		121	68	MULASAMUDRAM
		122	67	RAVUTTARAYANKUPPAM
		123	70	KUNAMANGALAM
		124	73	VELLAIYUR
	6. Thirunavalur	125	152	PERIYAPATTU
		126	153	ISWARAKANDANALLUR
		127	150	SIRULAPATTU
		128	149	PARAVANANDAL
		129	151	DEVIYANANDAL
		130	155	SOMASIPALAYAM
		131	154	SIRUPULIY UR
		132	158	MANALUR
		133	159	ODAIYANANDAL
		134	146	SEMMANANDAL
		135	147	SENJIKUPPAM
		136	145	AVALAM
		137	132	METTATT UR
		138	148	THIRUNAVVALUR
		139	143	PARIKKAL
		140	144	EDAIYALAM
		141	136	PERUMBAKKAM
		142	142	SENDAMANGA LAM
		143	141	VANDIPALAIYAM
		144	162	KALATTUR
		145	133	IRUNDAI
		146	135	KUVAKKAM
		147	134	KORATTUR
		148	157	MARUDUR(EAST)
		149	156	SIVAPATTANAM
		150	131	SIRUTTAN UR
		151	130	MADAPPATTU

ABSTRACT

Name of Division	Name of Taluk	No. of Firka	Name of the Firka	No. of Revenue Villages	Total No. of Revenue Villages
KALLAKURICHI	KALLAKURICHI	4	INDILI	25	93
			THIYAGADURUGAM	23	
			NAGALUR	31	
			KALLAKURICHI	14	
	SANKARAPURAM	5	VADAPONPARAPPI	24	133
			ARIYALUR	21	
			RISHIVANDIAYAM	30	
			ALATHUR	28	
			SANKARAPURAM	30	
	CHINNA SALEM	3	VADAKKANANDAL	17	63
			NAYINARPALAYAM	22	
			CHINNASALEM	24	
	KALVARAYAN HILLS	2	KALVARAYAN HILLS	18	44
VELLIMALAI			26		
TIRUKOVILUR	TIRUKOVILUR	3	TIRUPPALAPANDAL	25	74
			TIRUKOILUR	25	
			MANALURPET	24	
	ULUNDURPETTAI	6	ERAYIUR	26	151
			ELAVANASURKOTTAI	26	
			KALAMARUDUR	22	
			SENGURICHI	21	
			ULUNDURPET	29	
			THIRUNAVAILUR	27	
TOTAL					558

Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)

//True Copy//

my han
2/12/11/19
Section Officer

**TO BE PUBLISHED IN AN
EXTRA-ORDINARY ISSUE
OF TAMIL NADU
GOVERNMENT GAZETTE
DATED**

ABSTRACT

Revenue Administration - Jurisdiction -Bifurcation of Viluppuram District - Creation of Kallakurichi new District - Ordered - Notification under Tamil Nadu District Limits Act, 1865 - Issued.

**Revenue and Disaster Management Department,
Revenue Administration Wing, [RA 1(1)] Section**

G.O.(Ms) No.425

Dated: 12.11.2019

விகாரி, ஐப்பசி 26,
திருவள்ளூர் ஆண்டு 2050

Read:

G.O. (Ms) No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management [RA1(1)] Department, dated 12.11.2019.

ORDER:

The appended Notification will be published in an Extra-ordinary issue of the Tamil Nadu Government Gazette, dated 12.11.2019 and in the District Gazette of Viluppuram District.

2. The Works Manager, Government Central Press, Chennai - 79 is requested to send 100 copies each of the Notification to the Government and the Principal Secretary / Commissioner of Revenue Administration, Chennai - 5.

(By order of the Governor)

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

To

The Works Manager, Government Central Press, Chennai - 600 079.

(for Publication of Notification in an Extra - Ordinary issue of Tamil Nadu Government Gazette, Dated 12.11.2019)

The Principal Secretary / Commissioner of

Revenue Administration, Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.

The Additional Chief Secretary / Commissioner of Land

Administration, Chepauk, Chennai -600 005.

The Additional Chief Secretary / Commissioner of Land Reforms,
Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.

The Principal Secretary / Commissioner of Urban Land Ceiling
and Urban Land Tax, Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.

The Director of Survey and Settlement, Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005.

The Commissioner of Civil Supplies and Consumer Protection, Chennai - 600 005.

The District Collector, Viluppuram District.

The Special Officer concerned.

//p.t.o.//

The District Treasury Officer, Viluppuram District.
All District Collectors.
The Special Commissioner and Commissioner of
Treasuries and Accounts, Chennai - 600 035.
The Chief Electoral Officer, Public (Elections) Department, Chennai - 600 009.
The Post Master General, Chennai - 600 002.
The General Manager, Southern Railway Chennai - 600 003.
The Registrar General and Census Commissioner,
No.2/4, Mansingh Road, New Delhi - 100 011.
The Director of Information and Public Relations, Chennai - 600 009.
All Public Sector (Undertakings / Corporations of
Government of Tamil Nadu)
The Accountant General, (PAO) Chennai - 600 009.
The Accountant General, (A&E/G&SSA) Chennai-600 018.
The Pay and Accounts Officer, Chennai - 600 104.
The Director of Stationery and Printing, Chennai - 600 002.

Copy to:

All Secretaries to Government, Secretariat, Chennai - 600 009.
All Departments of Secretariat, Chennai - 600 009.
All Head of Departments.
All Sections in Revenue and Disaster Management Department,
Chennai - 600 009. (Follow-up action to be taken by the concerned section
in respect of sanction of Additional staff, further continuance, Furniture etc)
The Registrar, High Court of Madras, Chennai - 600 104. (with covering letter)
The Public (Special A) Department, Chennai - 600 009.
The Director of Census Operation, Ministry of Home Affairs, Chennai - 600 009.
The Public (Elections) Department, Chennai - 600 009. (4 copies)
The Hon'ble Chief Minister' Office, Chennai - 600 009.
The Special Personal Assistant to Hon'ble Minister (Revenue & Disaster
Management) Chennai - 600 009.
The Principal Private Secretary to the Principal Secretary,
Revenue and Disaster Management Department, Chennai - 600 009.
The Private Secretary to Chief Secretary to Government, Chennai - 600 009.
The Finance (Revenue) / (CMPC) Department, Chennai - 600 009.
Stock file / Spare copy.

//Forwarded by Order//

Section Officer

APPENDIX

NOTIFICATION

In exercise of the powers conferred by section 1 of the Tamil Nadu Districts Limits Act, 1865 (Tamil Nadu Act 1 of 1865), the Governor of Tamil Nadu hereby directs that with effect on and from 12th November 2019.

- (i) Viluppuram District is bifurcated into Viluppuram and Kallakurichi Districts as follows:-
- Viluppuram District with Head Quarters at Viluppuram.
 - Kallakurichi District with Head Quarters at Kallakurichi.
- (ii) Two Revenue Divisions of Viluppuram & Tindivanam and Nine Taluks of Viluppuram, Vikravandi, Vanur, Thiruvannainallur (new), Tindivanam, Gingee, Melmalaiyanur, Marakkanam & Kandachipuram shall constitute the Viluppuram District.
- (iii) Two Revenue Divisions of Kallakurichi & Tirukoilur and Six Taluks of Kallakurichi, Sankarapuram, Chinnasalem, Tirukoilur, Ulundurpet, & Kalvarayan Hills (new) shall constitute the Kallakurichi new District.

**Gagandeep Singh Bedi,
Principal Secretary to Government (FAC)**

//True Copy//

10/11/19
12/11/19
Section Officer

கருக்கம்

வருவாய் நிருவாகம் - ஆட்சி எல்லை - விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டத்தைப் பிரித்து கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம் உருவாக்கியது - இரு மாவட்டங்களில் ஆட்சி எல்லையில் சில மாற்றங்கள் ஏற்படுத்துதல் - திருத்தங்கள் மற்றும் ஆணைகள் - வெளியிடப்படுகின்றன.

வருவாய் மற்றும் பேரிடர் மேலாண்மை துறை, வருவாய் நிருவாக அலகு, வ.நி.1(1) பிரிவு

அரசாணை (நிலை) எண்.479

நாள்: 24.12.2019

விகாரி வருடம், மார்கழி 8,
திருவள்ளூர் ஆண்டு 2050

படிக்கவும்:-

1. அரசாணை எண்.424 வருவாய் மற்றும் பேரிடர் மேலாண்மைத்துறை வருவாய் நிர்வாகப் பிரிவு [வ.நி.1(1)] நாள் 12.11.2019.
2. மாவட்ட ஆட்சியர்கள், விழுப்புரம் மற்றும் கள்ளக்குறிச்சி ஆகியோர்களிடமிருந்து வரப்பெற்ற ஒருங்கிணைந்த கருத்துரு ந.க.எச்2/1362/2019, நாள் 22.12.2019.
3. முதன்மைச் செயலாளர் / வருவாய் நிருவாக ஆணையர் அவர்களின் கடித எண்.பணி 3(4) 1816/2019, நாள் 23.12.2019.

ஆணை:-

மேலே முதலாவதாகப் படிக்கப்பட்ட அரசாணையில், விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டத்தைப் பிரித்து கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம் உருவாக்கப்பட்டது. இது தொடர்பாக, இரு மாவட்டங்களின் ஆட்சி எல்லையிலும் சில மாற்றங்களை ஏற்படுத்துமாறு, பொது மக்களிடமிருந்து வரப்பெற்ற கோரிக்கைகளை ஏற்றும், நிருவாக நலன் கருதியும், இரு மாவட்ட ஆட்சியர்களிடமிருந்து முன்மொழிவுகள் பெறப்பட்டு, பரிசீலிக்கப்பட்டதின் அடிப்படையில் கீழ்க்கண்ட மாற்றங்களை மேலே மூன்றாவதாகப் படிக்கப்பட்ட கடிதத்தில் முதன்மைச் செயலாளர் / வருவாய் நிருவாக ஆணையர் பரிந்துரைத்துள்ளார்:-

- (i) கருவேப்பிலைப்பாளையம் என்ற குக்கிராமத்தின் ஒரு பகுதி, கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம், உளுந்தூர்பேட்டை வட்டம், திருநாவலூர் குறுவட்டம், சிறுத்தனூர் வருவாய் கிராமத்திலும், மற்றொரு பகுதி விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம், திருவெண்ணையல்லூர் வட்டம், அரசூர் குறுவட்டம், காந்தலவாடி வருவாய் கிராமத்திலும் அமைந்துள்ளது. அக்குக்கிராம பொது மக்கள் மேற்படி கிராமத்தை விழுப்புரம் மாவட்ட எல்லைக்குள் கொண்டு வருமாறு அளித்த

//த.பி.பா.//

கோரிக்கையினை ஏற்று, கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம், சிறுத்தனூர் வருவாய் கிராமத்தில் அடங்கியுள்ள கருவேப்பிலைப்பாளையம் 46.22.0 ஹெக்டேர் பரப்பளவினை பிரித்து, விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம், திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டம், அரசூர் குறுவட்டம், காந்தலவாடி வருவாய் கிராமத்துடன் இணைத்திடலாம்.

(ii) கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டத்திலுள்ள கொண்டசமுத்திரம், டி.கொளத்தூர், ஓட்டனந்தல், ஆழார், துலங்கம்பட்டு, பெரியசெவலை, சரவணப்பாக்கம் மற்றும் கொத்தனூர் ஆகிய 8 வருவாய் கிராமங்களும், விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம், திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டத்திற்கு அருகில் உள்ளதால், மேற்படி 8 வருவாய் கிராமங்களில் ஆழார், துலங்கம்பட்டு, பெரியசெவலை, சரவணப்பாக்கம் மற்றும் கொத்தனூர் ஆகிய 5 வருவாய் கிராமங்களை திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டம், திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் குறுவட்டத்திலும், கொண்டசமுத்திரம், டி.கொளத்தூர், ஓட்டனந்தல் ஆகிய 3 வருவாய் கிராமங்களை திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டம், சித்தலிங்கமடம் குறுவட்டத்திலும் இணைக்கலாம்.

(iii) விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம், திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டம், சித்தலிங்கமடம் குறுவட்டத்தில் அடங்கியுள்ள வடமருதூர், அத்தண்ட மருதூர், கொடியூர், டி.குன்னத்தூர், வீரணாம்பட்டு, வில்லிவலம், வடமலையனூர், எஸ்ராம்பட்டு, முதலூர், ஆவிகொளப்பாக்கம், வடக்குநெமிலி மற்றும் காட்டுப்பையூர் ஆகிய 12 வருவாய் கிராமங்களும், பிரிவினைக்கு முன்பு திருக்கோவிலூர் வட்டத்தில் இருந்ததாலும், அவை திருக்கோவிலூர் வட்ட தலைமையிடத்திற்கு அருகில் இருப்பதாலும், மேற்படி கிராமங்களை கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம், திருக்கோவிலூர் வட்டம், திருக்கோவிலூர் குறுவட்டத்துடன் சேர்க்கலாம். ஆதலால், தற்போது மேற்கண்ட குறுவட்டம் 37 கிராமங்களை கொண்ட பெரிய குறுவட்டமாக அமைகிறது. ஆதலால் ஆவிகொளப்பாக்கம் கிராமத்தை தலைமையிடமாகக் கொண்டு மேற்கண்ட 12 வருவாய் கிராமங்களை உள்ளடக்கிய புதிய குறுவட்டத்தினை உருவாக்கலாம்.

2. மேலும் முதன்மை செயலாளர்/ வருவாய் நிருவாக ஆணையர் அவர்கள் இரு மாவட்டங்களுக்கிடையேயான ஆட்சி எல்லை தொடர்பான மேற்குறிப்பிட்ட மாற்றங்களை ஏற்று, மேலே முதலாவதாகப் படிக்கப்பட்ட அரசாணை மற்றும் இணைப்புகளில் உரிய திருத்தங்களை வெளியிடவும், கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டத்தில் புதிதாக ஒரு குறுவட்டம் உருவாக்கிடவும், அரசைக் கோரியுள்ளார். மேலும், விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டத்தில் அமைவதாக அரசாணை (நிலை) எண்.424, வருவாய் மற்றும் பேரிடர் மேலாண்மை துறை (வ.நி.) நாள் 12.11.2019-ன் இணைப்பு I-இல் குறிப்பிட்டுள்ள முகையூர் ஊராட்சி ஒன்றியத்தின் பகுதிகள் விழுப்புரம் மற்றும் கள்ளக்குறிச்சி ஆகிய இரண்டு மாவட்டங்களிலும் உள்ளதால், அவ்வரசாணையின் இணைப்பில் உரிய திருத்தம் செய்திடவும் பரிந்துரைத்துள்ளார்.

//த.பி.பா.//

3. விழுப்புரம், கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்ட ஆட்சித் தலைவர்கள் மற்றும் முதன்மைச் செயலாளர் / வருவாய் நிருவாக ஆணையர் ஆகியோர்களின் கருத்துருகள் மற்றும் பரிந்துரைகளை அரசு நன்கு ஆய்வு செய்து, அவற்றை ஏற்று,-

- (i) கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம், உளுந்தூர்பேட்டை வட்டம், திருநாவலூர் குறுவட்டம், சிறுத்தனூர் வருவாய் கிராமத்தில் உள்ள கருவேப்பிலைப்பாளையம் குக்கிராமத்தின் ஒரு பகுதியான 46.22.0 ஹெக்டேர் பரப்பளவு, விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம், திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டம், அரகூர் குறுவட்டம், காந்தலவாடி வருவாய் கிராமத்தில் உள்ள கருவேப்பிலைப்பாளையம் குக்கிராம பகுதியுடன் இணைத்திடவும்,
- (ii) கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம், உளுந்தூர்பேட்டை வட்டம், களமருதூர் குறுவட்டத்திலுள்ள கொண்டசமுத்திரம், டி.கொளத்தூர், ஒட்டனந்தல், ஆழார், துலங்கம்பட்டு, பெரியசெவலை, சரவணப்பாக்கம் மற்றும் கொத்தனூர் ஆகிய 8 வருவாய் கிராமங்களில் ஆழார், துலங்கம்பட்டு, பெரியசெவலை, சரவணப்பாக்கம், மற்றும் கொத்தனூர், ஆகிய 5 வருவாய் கிராமங்கள், விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம், திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டம் மற்றும் திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் குறுவட்டத்திலும், கொண்டசமுத்திரம், டி.கொளத்தூர் மற்றும் ஒட்டனந்தல் ஆகிய 3 வருவாய் கிராமங்கள், விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம், திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டம், சித்தலிங்கமடம் குறுவட்டத்திலும் இணைத்திடவும்,
- (iii) விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம், திருவெண்ணெய்நல்லூர் வட்டம், சித்தலிங்கமடம் குறுவட்டத்திலுள்ள வடமருதூர், அத்தண்ட மருதூர், கொடியூர், டி.குன்னத்தூர், வீரணாம்பட்டு, வில்லிவலம், வடமலையனூர், எல்ராம்பட்டு, முதலூர், ஆவிகொளப்பாக்கம், வடக்குநெமிலி மற்றும் காட்டுப்பையூர் ஆகிய 12 வருவாய் கிராமங்களை கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம், திருக்கோவிலூர் வட்டத்தில் சேர்த்து மேற்படி 12 வருவாய் கிராமங்களை உள்ளடக்கி, ஆவிகொளப்பாக்கம் கிராமத்தினை தலைமையிடமாகக் கொண்டு ஆவிகொளப்பாக்கம் என்னும் புதிய குறுவட்டம் உருவாக்கவும்,
- (iv) விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டத்தில் அமைவதாக அரசாணை (நிலை) எண்.424, வருவாய் மற்றும் பேரிடர் மேலாண்மை துறை (வ.நி.) நாள் 12.11.2019-ன் இணைப்பு I-இல் குறிப்பிட்டுள்ள முகையூர் ஊராட்சி ஒன்றியத்தின் பகுதிகள் விழுப்புரம் மற்றும் கள்ளக்குறிச்சி ஆகிய இரண்டு மாவட்டங்களிலும் உள்ளதால், அவ்வரசாணையின் இணைப்பில் உரிய திருத்தம் செய்தும் ஆணையிடப்படுகிறது.

4. மேற்குறிப்பிட்ட ஆணைகளுக்கிணங்க, அரசாணை (நிலை) எண்.424, வருவாய் மற்றும் பேரிடர் மேலாண்மை துறை (வ.நி.) நாள் 12.11.2019 மற்றும் அதன் இணைப்புகளுக்கான உரிய திருத்தங்கள் இவ்வாணையின் இணைப்பில் வெளியிடப்படுகின்றன.

5. மேற்கண்ட ஆணைகளை செயல்படுத்திட தக்க நடவடிக்கை மேற்கொள்ளுமாறு முதன்மைச் செயலாளர்/ வருவாய் நிருவாக ஆணையர் கேட்டுக் கொள்ளப்படுகிறார்.

(ஆளுநரின் ஆணைப்படி)

அதூல்ய மிஸ்ரா,
அரசு கூடுதல் தலைமைச் செயலாளர்

பெறுநர்

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கூடுதல் தலைமைச் செயலாளர்/ நில நிருவாக ஆணையர், சென்னை-600 005.
முதன்மைச் செயலாளர், கூட்டுறவு, உணவு மற்றும்
நுகர்வோர் பாதுகாப்புத்துறை, சென்னை-600 009.
முதன்மைச் செயலாளர்/ ஆணையர், நகர்ப்புற நிலஉச்சவரம்பு(ம)
நகர்ப்புற நிலவரித்துறை, சென்னை-600 005.
கூடுதல் தலைமைச் செயலாளர்/ நிலச் சீர்திருத்த ஆணையர், சென்னை-600 005.
இயக்குநர், நில அளவை மற்றும் நிலவரித்திட்டம், சென்னை-600 005.
ஆணையர், குடிமைப் பொருள் மற்றும் நுகர்வோர்பாதுகாப்பு, சென்னை-600 005.
மாவட்ட ஆட்சித்தலைவர், விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம்.
மாவட்ட ஆட்சித்தலைவர், கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம்.
கருவூல அலுவலர், விழுப்புரம் மாவட்டம்.
கருவூல அலுவலர், கள்ளக்குறிச்சி மாவட்டம்.
மாநில கணக்காயர் (A&E), சென்னை-600 018.
மாநில கணக்காயர் (தணிக்கை), சென்னை-600 018. (பெயரிட்ட உறையில்)
மாநில கணக்காயர் (தணிக்கை), சென்னை-600 018.
மாநில கணக்காயர் (CAG) சென்னை-600 009.
மாநில கணக்காயர் (RAO) சென்னை-600 009.
இயக்குநர், எழுதுபொருள் அச்சுத்துறை, சென்னை-600 002.
அனைத்துத் துறை தலைவர்கள்/ அனைத்து மாவட்ட ஆட்சியர்கள்.
இயக்குநர், தகவல் மற்றும் மக்கள் தொடர்பு, சென்னை-600 009.
பதிவாளர், உயர்நீதிமன்றம், சென்னை-600 104.
தலைமை தேர்தல் அதிகாரி, பொது (தேர்தல்கள்) துறை, சென்னை-600 009.
ஆணையர், கருவூலக்கணக்கு துறை, சென்னை-600 015.
இயக்குநர், மக்கள் தொகை கணக்கெடுப்பு இயக்குநரகம்,
இராஜாஜி பவன், பெசன்ட் நகர், சென்னை-600 090.

நகல்:

முதலமைச்சர் அலுவலகம், சென்னை-600 009.
மாண்புமிகு அமைச்சர் (வருவாய் (ம) பேரிடர் மேலாண்மை)
அவர்களின் சிறப்பு நேர்முக உதவியாளர், சென்னை-600 009.
கூடுதல் தலைமைச் செயலாளர், (வருவாய் (ம) பேரிடர் மேலாண்மைத்துறை)
அவர்களின் தனிச் செயலாளர், சென்னை-600 009.
நிதித் (வ.செ.பொது-I/ வ.செ.பொது-II/ வருவாய்/கக-3/
கூஉ(ம)நுபா/ பொதுப்பணி- I/மை.மஆபி) துறை, சென்னை- 600 009.
சிறப்புத் திட்ட அமலாக்கத் துறை, சென்னை-600 009.
இருப்பு கோப்பு / உதிரி.

//ஆணைப்படி அனுப்பப்படுகிறது//

THY h n n
20/12/19
பிரிவு அலுவலர்

ANNEXURE

**[Vide G.O.(Ms.)No.479, Revenue and Disaster Management Department,
Revenue Administration Wing [RA1(1)] Section, Dated 24.12.2019]**

**Amendment for the G.O.(Ms.)No.424, Revenue and Disaster Management
Department, Revenue Administration Wing [RA1(1)] Section,
Dated.12.11.2019**

- 1) In Para 3 of the said G.O,
 - a) Instead of para (III), the following paras shall be substituted Namely,
 - (iii) Thiruvonnainallur new Taluk is formed with Head Quarters at Thiruvonnainallur with 3 Firkas (66 Villages) viz., Thiruvonnainallur (30 Villages) (By adding 5 Villages from Kalamarudur Firka of existing Ulundurpet Taluk), Sithalingamadam (12 Villages) (By deleting 12 Villages from existing Sithalingamadam Firka and adding 3 Villages from Kalamarudur Firka of existing Ulundurpet Taluk) and Arasur Firka (24 Villages) of the existing Ulundurpet Taluk are attached with Viluppuram Revenue Division and Viluppuram District. (Details are indicated in Annexure - III in this order)
- 2) In Annexure-I of the G.O.-
 - a) In Serial No.2 (Area, Sq.Km.), Serial No.3 (Population), Serial No.9 (No. of Panchayat unions with name), Serial No.11(No.of Firkas), Serial No.12 (No. of Revenue Villages) & Serial No.13 (No. of Village Panchayats) the following shall be substituted namely,

SI.No.	Description	Viluppuram District before Bifurcation	Kallakurichi New District	Viluppuram District after Bifurcation
2.	Area (Sq.Km)	7245.91(Sq.Km)	3530.58 (Sq.Km)	3715.33 (Sq.Km)
3.	Population	3463284	1377494	2085790
9.	No. of Panchayat unions with name		10. Mugaiyur (part) to be added	12. Mugaiyur (part)
11.	No. of Firkas	57	24*	34
12.	No.of Revenue Villages	1490	562	928
13.	No.of Village Panchayats	1099	412	687

*Including newly created Avikulapakkam Firka in Tirukoilur Taluk

3. In Annexure - III of the G.O., the following shall be substituted namely,

SI.No.	Details	Thiruvannainallur New Taluk
2.	Area (Sq.Km)	238.22
3.	Population	153741
11	No.of Revenue Villages	66
12.	No.of Village Panchayats	52

4. In Annexure - V of the G.O., the following shall be substituted against entries in Thiruvannainallur (New Taluk)

Division	Taluks	Population	Area in Sq. Kms.	No. of Firkas	No. of villages	No. of panchayat unions	No. of municipalities	No. of town Panchayats
Viluppuram	Viluppuram	421957	416.00	4	123	3	1	2
	Vikravandi	293454	478.00	4	116	1	--	1
	Vanur	195476	451.89	4	81	1	--	1
	Kandachipuram	151027	234.00	2	62	1	--	1
	Thiruvannainallur (new)	153741	238.22	3	66	1	-	-
Tindivanam	Tindivanam	316342	657.22	7	174	3	1	--
	Gingee	283025	580.00	4	166	1	--	2
	Melmalaiyanur	139728	345.00	3	80	1	--	--
	Marakkanam	131040	315.00	3	60	1	--	1
Total		2085790	3715.33	34	928	13	02	08

5. In Annexure - VI of the G.O., the following shall be substituted against entries in Ulundurpet Taluk and Tirukoilur Taluk.

Division	Taluk	Population	Area in Sq.Kms.	No.of Firkas	No.of Villages	No.of Panchayat Unions	No.of Municipalities	No.of town Panchayats
Tirukoilur	Tirukoilur	203092	347.30	4*	86	1	-	2
	Ulundurpet	299751	620.34	6	143	2	-	1
Kallakurichi	Kallakurichi	277303	538.58	4	93	2	1	1
	Sankarapuram	361975	1045.38	5	133	2	-	1
	Chinnasalem	194348	428.28	3	63	1	-	2
	Kalvarayan Hills (new)	41025	550.70	2	44	1	-	-
Total		1377494	3530.58	24	562	09	01	07

*Including newly created Avikulapakkam Firka in Tirukoilur Taluk

6. In Annexure - VII of the G.O., the following shall be substituted against entries in Thiruvannainallur Taluk

Taluks in Viluppuram Distict			No.of Firkas			No.of Revenue Villages		
			Existing	Addition	Newly Restructured	Existing	Addition	Newly Restructured
Viluppuram Division	1	Viluppuram	4	0	4	123	0	123
	2	Vikkaravandi	4	0	4	116	0	116
	3	Vanur	4	0	4	81	0	81
	4	Kandachipuram	2	0	2	62	0	62
	5	Thiruvannainallur (newly proposed Taluk)	0	3	3	0	66	66
Tindivanam Division	1	Tindivanam	7	0	7	174	0	174
	2	Marakkanam	3	0	3	60	0	60
	3	Gingee	4	0	4	166	0	166
	4	Melmalayanur	3	0	3	80	0	80
Total			31	3	34	862	66	928

7. In Annexure - VIII of the G.O., the following shall be substituted against entries in Ulundurpet Taluk

Taluks in new Kallakurichi District			No. of Firkas			No.of Revenue Villages		
			Existing	Addition / Deletion	Newly restructure	Existing	Addition / Deletion	Newly restructure
Kallakurichi Revenue Division	1	Kallakurichi	4	0	4	93	0	93
	2	Chinnasalem	4	-1	3	89	-26	63
	3	Sankarapuram	6	-1	5	151	-18	133
	4	Kalvarayan Hills (newly proposed Taluk)	0	2	2	0	44	44

Tirukoilur Revenue Division	1	Tirukoilur	5	+1 -2	4*	120	-46 +12	86
	2	Ulundurpet	7	-1	6	175	-32	143
TOTAL			26	+3 -5	24	628	-122 +56	562

*Including newly created Avikulapakkam Firka in Tirukoilur Taluk

8. In Annexure - X of the G.O., the following Villages shall be added with Thiruvannainallur Taluk against Sithalingamadam Firka after Konalavadi (Tirukoilur)

Name of the Taluk	Name of the Firka	Village No.	Name of the Village
II. THIRUVENNAINALLUR (New)	I. SITHALINGAMADAM	98	KONDASAMUDRAM
		99	T. KOLATHUR
		100	ODDANANDAL

9. In Annexure - X of the G.O., the following Villages shall be added with Thiruvannainallur Taluk against Thiruvannainallur Firka after Malaiyampattu Village.

Name of the Taluk	Name of the Firka	Village No.	Name of the Village
II. THIRUVENNAINALLUR (New)	2. THIRUVENNAINALLUR	101	AMoor
		102	THULANGAMPATTU
		103	PERIYASEVALAI
		104	SARAVANAPPAKKAM
		105	KOTTANUR

10. In Annexure - X of the G.O., the following Villages shall be deleted from Thiruvannainallur Taluk in Sithalingamadam Firka

Name of the Taluk	Name of the Firka	Village No.	Name of the Village
II. THIRUVENNAINALLUR	I. SITHALINGAMADAM	77	VADAKKUNEMALI
		78	ATTANDAMARUDUR
		76	MUDALUR
		75	AVIKULAPAKKAM
		74	KATTUPPAIYUR
		84	ELRAMBATTU
		83	KODIYUR
		82	KUNNATTUR (THIRUVENNAINALLUR)

		89	VIRANAMBATTU
		79	MARUDUR (VADA)
		85	MALAIYANUR (VADA)
		86	VILLIVALAM

Abstract (Page No. 20 in said G.O.) shall be read as follows

Name of the District	Name of the Division	Name of the Taluk	No. of Firka	No. of Revenue Villages
VILUPPURAM	VILUPPURAM	1) VILUPPURAM	4	123
		2) THIRUVENNAINALLUR (NEW)**	3	66
		3) KANDACHIPURAM	2	62
		4) VIKRAVANDI	4	116
		5) VANUR	4	81
	TINDIVANAM	6) TINDIVANAM	7	174
		7) GINGEE	4	166
		8) MELMALAYANUR	3	80
		9) MARAKKANAM	3	60
			Total	34

** Sittalingamadam Firka, Thiruvonnainallur Firka Detached from Tirukoilur Taluk, Aarasur Firka Detached from Ulundurpet Taluk and added to Viluppuram Division.

11. In Annexure - XI of the G.O., the following Villages shall be deleted from Ulundurpet Taluk, Kalamarudur Firka

Name of the Taluk	Name of the Firka	Village No.	Name of the Village
V. Ulundurpet	3. Kalamarudur	103	PERIYASEVALAI
		101	AMoor
		102	THULANGAMPATTU
		104	SARAVANAPPAKKAM
		105	KOTTANUR
		99	T.KOLATHUR
		98	KONDASAMUDRAM
		100	ODDANANDAL

12. In Annexure - XI of the G.O., the following Villages shall be added in Tirukoilur Taluk under new Avikulapakkam Firka

Name of the Taluk	Name of the Firka	Village No.	Name of the Village
V. TIRUKOILUR	4. Avikulapakkam Firka (new)*	77	VADAKKUNEMALI
		78	ATTANDAMARUDUR
		76	MUDALUR
		75	AVIKULAPAKKAM
		74	KATTUPPAIYUR
		84	ELRAMBATTU
		83	KODIYUR
		82	KUNNATTUR (THIRUVENNAINALLUR)
		89	VIRANAMBATTU
		79	MARUDUR (VADA)
		85	MALAIYANUR (VADA)
		86	VILLIVALAM

*Including newly created Avikulapakkam Firka in Tirukoilur Taluk

13. Abstract (Page No. 13 in said G.O.) shall be read as follows

Name of the Division	Name of the Taluk	No. of Firka	Name of the Firka	No. of Revenue Village	Total No. of Revenue Villages
KALLAKURICHI	KALLAKURICHI	4	INDILI	25	93
			THIYAGADURUGAM	23	
			NAGALUR	31	
			KALLAKURICHI	14	
	SANKARAPURAM	5	VADAPONPARAPPI	24	133
			ARIYALUR	21	
			RISHIVANDIAYAM	30	
			ALATHUR	28	
			SANKARAPURAM	30	
	CHINNASALEM	3	VADAKKANANDAL	17	63
			NAYINARPALAYAM	22	
			CHINNASALEM	24	
	KALVARAYAN HILLS	2	KALVARAYAN HILLS	18	44
VELLIMALAI			26		

TIRUKOILUR	TIRUKOILUR	4	TIRUPPALAPANDAL	25	86
			TIRUKOILUR	25	
			MANALURPET	24	
			AVIKULAPAKKAM	12	
	ULUNDURPET	6	ERAIYIUR	26	143
			ELAVANASURKOTTAI	26	
			KALAMARUDUR	14	
			SENGURICHI	21	
			ULUNDURPET	29	
			THIRUNAVVALUR	27	
			TOTAL	562	562

**Atulya Misra,
Additional Chief Secretary to Government**

//True Copy//

Section Officer